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Abstract:

The Update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics already started in 2025 and required input earlier than originally anticipated. IMCC adapted its workplan and prepared the required input documents as a world-wide collaboration and as a key part of the MuCol programme.

The process initially demanded the submission of a concise 10-page proposal. A questionnaire to be completed at the same time has been distributed.

Subsequently, two further questionnaires have been distributed. The first by the Strategy Working Group 2a asking for additional specific input on the accelerator design and technical readiness. The second by the Knowledge Transfer and Innovation Working Group.

IMCC provided all of these documents. They are documented in this report.

The current focus is to finish a detailed report describing the physics case, status, progress and R&D programme for the muon collider. An R&D task force is preparing the resource-loading of the R&D programme.

MuCol Consortium, 2026

For more information on MuCol, its partners and contributors please see <https://mucol.web.cern.ch/>

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The Muon Collider

Input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics – 2026 update

The Muon Collider

Input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics - 2026 update

The International Muon Collider Collaboration

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Abstract

Muons offer a unique opportunity to build a compact high-energy electroweak collider at the 10 TeV scale. A Muon Collider enables direct access to the underlying simplicity of the Standard Model and unparalleled reach beyond it. It will be a paradigm-shifting tool for particle physics representing the first collider to combine the high-energy reach of a proton collider and the high precision of an electron-positron collider, yielding a physics potential significantly greater than the sum of its individual parts. A high-energy muon collider is the natural next step in the exploration of fundamental physics after the HL-LHC and a natural complement to a future low-energy Higgs factory. Such a facility would significantly broaden the scope of particle colliders, engaging the many frontiers of the high energy community.

The last European Strategy for Particle Physics Update and later the Particle Physics Project Prioritisation Panel in the US requested a study of the muon collider, which is being carried on by the International Muon Collider Collaboration. In this comprehensive document we present the physics case, the state of the work on accelerator design and technology, and propose an R&D project that can make the muon collider a reality.

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Introduction and Overview

The muon collider is a unique, compact, high-energy electroweak collider concept which will produce, cool, accelerate and collide two single-bunch muon beams of opposite charge. It is a paradigm-shifting tool for particle physics representing the first collider to combine the high-energy reach of a hadron collider and the high precision of a lepton collider, yielding a physics potential significantly greater than the sum of its individual parts.

The muon collider potential motivates a growing community, with substantial international interest and enthusiasm, with many calling for the scientific community to aim high and "*shoot for the muon*". The innovative nature of the muon collider in accelerator, detector and magnet technologies has attracted a vibrant community of early career researchers across all regions, many of whom are key designers of systems throughout the accelerator complex. This is an important asset for the muon collider and for the fields of accelerator and particle physics in general. This report contains the proposals and steps necessary to make the muon collider a reality, even within the next generation of high-energy particle physics facilities. Substantial improvements of the design and several enabling technologies are essential to achieve this goal. However, it is important to emphasise that no technological showstoppers have been identified in any studies of the muon collider.

1 The muon collider concept

The baseline muon collider design is a 10 TeV centre-of-mass collider providing an integrated luminosity of 10 ab^{-1} [1]. An initial stage that can be implemented by around 2050 is also considered [2].

Fig. 1: Conceptual layout of the muon collider.

The design of the muon collider is based on a concept, which was developed by the U.S. Muon Accelerator Programme (MAP) until 2017 [3]. The design is now being progressed by the International Muon Collider Collaboration (IMCC) [4]. A schematic layout of the collider is shown in Figure 1 and contains the following key areas:

1. The **proton driver** (blue box in the diagram) produces a short, high-intensity proton pulse.
2. This pulse hits the **target** (indigo) and produces pions. The decay channel guides the pions and forms a beam with the resulting muons via a buncher and phase rotator system.
3. Several **cooling** stages (purple) reduce the longitudinal and transverse emittance of the beam using a sequence of absorbers and RF cavities in a high magnetic field.
4. A system of a linac and two recirculating linacs **accelerate** (light red) the beams to 63 GeV followed by a sequence of high-energy accelerator rings which reach 1.5 TeV or 5 TeV.
5. Finally the beams are injected at full energy into the **collider** ring (red). Here, they will circulate and collide within the detectors until they decay.

Table 1 shows the key parameters for a site independent implementation of a 3 TeV and a 10 TeV centre-of-mass energy stage. These are target parameters conceived to explore the limits of each technology and design. If they can be fully met, the integrated luminosity goal could be reached within five years (or 2.5 years, with two detectors) of full luminosity operation. This provides margin for further design and technology studies and a realistic ramp-up of the luminosity.

An implementation at CERN is under consideration and could reuse the existing SPS and LHC tunnels to accelerate the muon beam. This design could reach a centre-of-mass collision energy of up to 7.6 TeV and a practical initial energy stage could reach up to 3.2 TeV, depending on the layout. The significant reduction of civil engineering and associated environmental impact may justify the slight reduction in physics scope.

Example parameters for a CERN implementation are shown assuming that a single collider ring tunnel is constructed and used for both energy stages, which is consistent with the use of Nb₃Sn magnets at full energy. If two independent collider rings at CERN are used with Nb₃Sn dipoles for the 3.2 TeV and high-temperature superconductors (HTS) for the 7.6 TeV stage, the luminosities would increase to $2 \times 10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and $10.1 \times 10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, respectively. Use of fast-ramping HTS magnets in the muon acceleration might enable increase of the final energy stage to close to 10 TeV; R&D is required to verify that such an option is practical.

Table 1: Tentative target parameters for a muon collider at different energies. The site independent scenario uses Nb₃Sn technology in the collider ring that is consistent with a project implementation by 2050. The CERN scenario reuses the SPS and LHC tunnels and assumes a 11 km collider tunnel, while the initial studies assumed 10 km. The estimated luminosity refers to the value that can be reached if all target specifications can be reached, including beam-beam effects.

Parameter	Symbol	unit	Site independent		CERN	
			Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 1	Stage 2
Centre-of-mass energy	E_{cm}	TeV	3	10	3.2	7.6
Target integrated luminosity	$\int \mathcal{L}_{\text{target}}$	ab ⁻¹	1	10	1	10
Estimated luminosity	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{estimated}}$	$10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.8	17.5	0.9	7.9
Collider circumference	C_{coll}	km	4.5	11.4	11	11
Collider arc peak field	B_{arc}	T	11	14	4.8	11
Collider dipole technology			Nb ₃ Sn	HTS	NbTi	Nb ₃ Sn or HTS

2 Physics Case

A muon collider is a high-energy electroweak collider. It can access directly and precisely the underlying simplicity of the Standard Model (SM) in its high-energy regime of “unbroken” electroweak symmetry. This makes it an ideal and unique machine to investigate fundamental questions about our universe – both long-held ones and more recent ones sparked by the LHC. Simultaneously, it is a paradigm-shifting tool for particle physics representing the first high-energy, high-precision compact collider. It combines the precision of a lepton collider with the energy reach of a hadron collider, yielding a physics potential significantly greater than the sum of its individual parts. This enables unparalleled exploration of the Electroweak-Higgs Unification era that we have entered since the discovery of the Higgs. We can now hope to answer the question of why electroweak symmetry breaking (EWSB) occurs by directly probing the transition between the “broken” and “unbroken” symmetry regimes. Furthermore, we can address the phase diagram of EWSB and quantitatively investigate the earliest moments in our universe and its ultimate fate. With high-energy EW collisions we can also search for physics beyond the SM directly using a muon collider as an unrivaled EW discovery machine. These same high-energy high precision collisions allow us also to probe new physics to scales far beyond the collider’s energy and study the Standard Model in new domains where new phenomena emerge.

For example, a muon collider can make exquisite measurements of TeV-scale vector boson scattering. This is due to the inherently quantum and relativistic effect of abundant effective vector bosons

contained in a high-energy muon, which gives rise to large collision rates with low backgrounds. Such measurements enable the first precision experimental tests of the “unitarization” of massive gauge boson scattering, arguably the foremost prediction of Electroweak symmetry breaking. High-energy, high-precision studies of the Higgs and vector bosons also give the first detailed probes of the “Electroweak symmetry restoration” realm within the SM. The high-energy nature of the muon collider also enables new insights into, and tests of, the “quantum compositeness” of particles. This is ideally studied in Electroweak processes due to their perturbative and thus in principle calculable nature (unlike the strong interactions), and the physical mass gap that makes “particles” fully well defined as asymptotic states unlike in Quantum Electrodynamics (QED). Finally, the intrinsic nature of a high-energy muon collider provides the most abundant and best characterized source of high-energy neutrino-target collisions conceived thus far. The neutrino physics program at a muon collider provides a high-energy complement to current and future long-baseline neutrino experiments.

Fig. 2: The ground-breaking nature of the muon collider physics perspectives and its contemporary pertinence in the particle physics landscape after the LHC is well represented by the enthusiastic reaction of the theory community to the muon collider study plans initiated by the 2020 ESPPU. The number of papers on muon colliders in the hep-ph category is reported in blue on the left panel. The right panel summarises the core directions of the physics case.

A muon collider simultaneously offers numerous pathways to searching for Beyond Standard Model (BSM) physics by utilizing the energy reach, precision measurement capabilities, and the combination thereof. The same abundant vector boson scattering that enables exploration of new SM phenomena also furnishes a next-generation Higgs factory. In certain channels this allows an order of magnitude or more improvement in the understanding of Higgs properties, including its potential. This allows one to experimentally probe BSM contributions that could change the nature of the EW phase transition and baryogenesis, the ultimate fate of our vacuum and the “Higgs portal” to hidden sectors. Furthermore the energy reach of a muon collider allows one to test the origin of any deviation from SM properties found in a precision measurement at the same collider, and by extension any previous Higgs Factory. The combination of precision and energy also allows one to probe BSM possibilities such as “Higgs compositeness” up to the $\mathcal{O}(100)$ TeV scale, far beyond the reach of any other proposed collider. Reaching the 10 TeV scale directly also enables unmatched probes of new EW particles such as those responsible for the simplest dark matter paradigms, or alternatively probing the possibility of new gauge forces in many cases to unrivaled scales. The combination of energy and precision also revolutionises flavor physics by enabling direct tests of fermions interactions, with a new physics scale reach that is comparable or superior to the one attainable by traditional studies of meson or leptons decays. This includes neutral current flavor tests sensitive to mediators at the 100 TeV scale, while also enabling new windows into

SM flavor in the Higgs sector and potential explanations of neutrino masses with Heavy Neutral Lepton searches.

The impressive physics potential of a muon collider is enabled by both its energy reach as well as its high luminosity. The luminosity goal of 10 TeV with 10 ab^{-1} is naturally consistent with the emittance targets from cooling and the inherent increase of luminosity power efficiency at high-energy. While most studies have been performed for these parameters, it's important to note that the bulk of the physics potential is only mildly affected by a slight change in energy or an order of magnitude change in luminosity. Furthermore, a muon collider is an innately stageable project in both luminosity and energy given a common front end for muon production and cooling. With a staged approach, considerable technical and financial risk could be retired and physics progress can be achieved along the path to the highest energies. Low energy stages could provide direct measurements of the Higgs width or experimentally and theoretically precise measurements of the top mass. Such low-energy muon colliders could be also considered as an independent satellite project at the muon collider complex. A 3 or 3.2 TeV stage can offer the first significant step beyond the HL-LHC in understanding the Higgs potential as well as testing certain Dark Matter (DM) candidates. A 7.6 TeV stage at CERN would extend our understanding of EWSB even further allowing a differential test of EW restoration, especially relevant if luminosity goals are relaxed in the pursuit of the highest energies. Furthermore, while 10 TeV is the ultimate goal of this study, it is not the final goal of particle colliders nor the highest conceivable energy of a muon collider in the far future.

Successfully building a muon collider allows us to reset the collider landscape with this paradigm shifting tool. Muon collider investment now lays the groundwork for coming generations to explore nature *directly* at even shorter distances, in likely the only sustainable and technically practical way for the future of High-Energy Physics (HEP).

3 Detector

The design of dedicated experiments to take data at the collider interaction points has sparked a lively environment that allowed the community to make fast progress in just a few years. The detector design is still in its infancy, but it is already possible to make substantive statements about the technological requirements, expected performance, and opportunities for further improvement.

Requirements were spelled out in terms of detector acceptance, particle detection and identification efficiency, as well as to resolutions on the various particle properties inferred by the instrumental measurements. They were outlined in terms of “baseline” and “aspirational” targets, corresponding, respectively, to the requirements to fully exploit the physics potential of the machine and a more ambitious set of performances comparable to those targeted by Higgs/Top/Electroweak-factories. These targets are summarised in Table 2.

An initial detector, optimised for operation at a $\sqrt{s} = 3 \text{ TeV}$ muon collider, was extensively studied and demonstrated the feasibility of the physics programme. Recent work focused on developing the first detector designs for a $\sqrt{s} = 10 \text{ TeV}$ machine. Two distinct detector concepts have been developed: MUSIC (MUon System for Interesting Collisions) and MAIA (Muon Accelerator Instrumented Apparatus). Both designs, shown in Figure 3, envision a multi-purpose detector sharing a similar structure: a cylinder 11.4 m long with a diameter of 12.8 m. They comprise typical collider detector instrumentation, such as an all-silicon tracking system, an electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL), a hadron calorimeter (HCAL), and a muon sub-detector. Superconducting solenoids are used to provide bending power for the measurement of charged particle momenta within the tracking system. The design work follows the concept already developed for $\sqrt{s} = 3 \text{ TeV}$, with modifications to account for the higher energy. The main differences between the two detector concepts lie in the placement of the solenoid (after the tracker in MAIA and between ECAL and the HCAL in MUSIC) and the technologies selected for the ECAL (Si-W for MAIA and semihomogeneous crystals for MUSIC).

Table 2: Preliminary summary of the “baseline” and “aspirational” targets for selected key metrics for a 10 TeV muon collider.

Requirement	Baseline	Aspirational
Angular acceptance $\eta = -\log(\tan(\theta/2))$	$ \eta < 2.5$	$ \eta < 4$
Minimum tracking distance [cm]	~ 3	< 3
Forward muons ($\eta > 5$)	tag	$\sigma_p/p \sim 10\%$
Track σ_{p_T}/p_T^2 [GeV^{-1}]	4×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}
Photon energy resolution	$0.2/\sqrt{E}$	$0.1/\sqrt{E}$
Neutral hadron energy resolution	$0.4/\sqrt{E}$	$0.2/\sqrt{E}$
Timing resolution (tracker) [ps]	$\sim 30 - 60$	$\sim 10 - 30$
Timing resolution (calorimeters) [ps]	100	10
Timing resolution (muon system) [ps]	~ 50 for $ \eta > 2.5$	< 50 for $ \eta > 2.5$
Flavour tagging	b vs c	b vs c , s -tagging
Boosted hadronic resonance identification	h vs W/Z	W vs Z

Fig. 3: Layout of the MUSIC (left) and MAIA (right) detector concepts

High levels of beam-induced background in the detector pose unprecedented challenges for the reconstruction and identification of particles produced in muon collisions. Studies based on detailed simulations of the MAIA and MUSIC detector concepts were carried out. These studies used state-of-the-art FLUKA simulations to account for the beam backgrounds produced by the decays in the latest accelerator lattice, and GUINEA-PIG predictions to study the effects of incoherent pair production at the interaction point. The detector response was studied to develop initial background-mitigation measures. In both cases, the results indicate that the background effects on the detector response can be minimised to a degree that approaches the aspirational goals.

Research and development over the next decade must focus on developing the necessary technologies, tools, and crucial expertise to design and construct state-of-the-art detectors for this future machine. At the muon collider, most detector components must simultaneously optimize position resolution, timing capability, radiation hardness, data transmission, and on-detector background rejection, all while maintaining low-mass and low-power consumption. Many of these technical challenges align with ongoing research in other initiatives, such as the LHC and Higgs/Top/EW-factory R&D programs. However, the development effort must also address challenges unique to the muon collider, including its harsh radiation environment, the need to suppress significant beam-induced backgrounds, and the requirements for high-precision calorimetry to measure significantly higher energy physics objects.

The R&D program is organised around three main areas: simulation and performance, technology and computing. In technological R&D, multiple technologies will be investigated in the first phase of the

work. The choices are expected to consolidate after the first four to six years and resources will transfer to the identified technologies needed for the chosen detectors designs. Coverage across areas for items relevant for the same sub-detectors is also ensured. Among all tasks that have been identified, ASICs and detector magnets have been identified as critical components requiring extended development timelines and should therefore be prioritized to ensure readiness for detector construction.

4 Readiness and muon collider challenges

The IMCC, the Muon Beam Panel of the Laboratory Directors Group (LDG) and the Snowmass process in the U.S. have all assessed the muon collider challenges with the support of the global community [5, 6]. Key conclusions are that, although the muon collider concept is less mature than several linear collider concepts, no insurmountable obstacles have been identified, and that important design and technical challenges have to be addressed with a coherent international effort. Furthermore, past work, in particular within the U.S. Muon Accelerator Programme (MAP) [3], has demonstrated several key technologies and concepts, and gives confidence that the overall Muon Collider concept is viable. Since then further component designs and technologies have been developed that provide increased confidence that one can cool the initially diffuse beam and accelerate it to multi-TeV energy on a time scale compatible with the muon lifetime. However, a fully integrated design has yet to be developed and full demonstrations of technology are required.

Following the last European Strategy, the IMCC has been formed with the goal to establish whether the investment into an important R&D programme on the muon collider is justified. A prioritised work programme has been developed by the LDG with this goal and is being implemented by IMCC. Resources have been made by the 58 member institutions, several other partners and the European Union. Following discussions with DoE representatives, an addendum to the CERN-DoE agreement is prepared and currently being reviewed by DoE. At this point, progress in several areas is limited by resources and additional resources are being sought across the collaboration, in parallel with the processes to include new partners. The R&D programme thus addresses priority challenges.

The IMCC programme prepares the way towards a conceptual design report (CDR) and a demonstration programme for a muon collider. The IMCC studies physics potential, detector design, accelerator design and performance studies. Studies assess technology maturity and develop critical designs to understand key challenges.

Parameters for the **proton driver** were developed based on existing facilities and simulations of key systems for a high-intensity 5 GeV or 10 GeV beam. Heat and radiation load in the **target** area was assessed for 2 MW proton beam power; a target and shielding design was developed that adequately protects the capture solenoid and limits damage to the graphite target rod. Extraction of the spent proton beam at the target has been identified as a potential technical issue.

The **muon cooling** system reduces the 6D beam size (emittance) to improve luminosity, and has been optimised from previous designs. The system delivers transverse and longitudinal emittances of 22.5 μm and 7 meV s respectively. The longitudinal emittance is almost a factor 3 better than the target parameters but the transmission is 20 % lower than target. Optimisation continues by matching between cooling stages, integrating components within the cooling cell and improving the longitudinal beam capture section. Beam-loading and heat-load on the hydrogen absorbers have been identified as technical issues.

Low-energy **acceleration** solutions have been found for the LINAC and the second recirculating linear accelerator. Simulation of the high-energy acceleration has been performed including single-turn and multi-turn wakefields and with counter-rotating beams. The lattice exceeds the target values for transmission. Suitable emittance control has been demonstrated in the absence of errors. Lattice errors may impact the beam quality and this is a focus of ongoing studies.

The **collider** ring at 10 TeV centre-of-mass energy and $\beta^*=1.5$ mm must deliver a short bunch

with a large energy spread to avoid luminosity dilution from the hour-glass effect. Challenges arise from controlling chromatic aberration in the ring despite the 0.1% RMS momentum spread. The current β^* lattice has a reduction in energy acceptance compared to the target parameters. Magnet misalignments may reduce performance further, especially as the magnets will be periodically moved ± 1 mrad, to dilute the neutrino flux. Designs are ongoing to improve energy acceptance. The potential improvement in longitudinal cooling may alleviate the shortfall.

The **magnet team** has developed conceptual designs for critical magnet systems, including: a 1.2 m bore and 20 T *target solenoid*; *cooling solenoids* with achievable values for radial and hoop stress, stored energy, current density and fields up to 40 T; *rapidly pulsed normal-conducting* ± 1.8 T magnets for the accelerator system with high-efficiency power converters that require acceptable wall-plug power and; *high-field dipoles*, quadrupoles and combined-function magnets including appropriate shielding from muon decay electrons. A resource-loaded programme for magnet hardware development, which is on the muon collider facility critical path, has been assessed and is discussed below.

The **RF team** has developed 352 and 704 MHz normal conducting RF cavity designs for the cooling system. The *cooling RF cavities* are challenging owing to tight integration with the solenoids and up to 32 MV/m required electric field. Power couplers have been developed to minimise interference with neighbouring equipment. *High-energy acceleration cavities* have been developed assuming 1.3 GHz RF structures. The required layout of RF stations and impact on the beam quality has been assessed. It has been integrated within the overall lattice.

A **Muon Cooling Demonstration** programme has been proposed based on a typical section of the cooling channel. An integrated engineering design has been developed. Candidate sites at CERN, Fermilab and other laboratories have been identified. Concepts for layout and beam optics design of the beam transport sections have been assessed. The programme, including magnet and RF cavity R&D, has been developed into a resource-loaded timeline. The Demonstrator is also on the muon collider facility critical path and implementation is discussed below.

Fig. 4: Conceptual layout of the muon collider at CERN (left) and Fermilab (right).

Civil engineering studies at CERN indicate that the surface installations of the accelerator facility could be constructed fully on CERN land and that **the SPS and LHC tunnels could be reused** to host the accelerator rings, thus minimising the overall civil engineering. The proton complex would be located on the Meyrin site. Figure 4 (left) shows a layout. The beam would be transported through the SPS tunnel to the Prevezin site where the cooling and initial linacs would be located in cut-and-cover tunnels. The beam is injected into the SPS then the LHC and finally into a new 10 km long collider ring. It may be possible to maintain the current SPS in parallel to the muon collider. A similar siting

study, including investigation of how the existing and planned infrastructure can be used, is underway for Fermilab and the preliminary layout, constrained within the boundaries of the Fermilab site, is shown in Figure 4 (right). The exact parameters of the collider sited at Fermilab are to be refined taking into account findings from the study.

Muon decays produce neutrinos that will exit the earth’s surface far from the accelerator facility. These neutrinos will enable a unique experimental programme that goes far beyond current state-of-the-art programmes such as FASER ν . In this case neutrino detectors would be installed on the surface where the neutrino beam emerges. A suitable implementation has been identified at CERN. The neutrinos arising from the rest of the facility must be diluted so that there is negligible radiation outside the CERN site, comparable to the impact of the LHC. A system of movers are required in collider arcs to displace the magnets vertically to achieve this. Tentative studies indicate that it is possible to have a negligible impact on the environment. Further optimisation and expansion of the studies to the full complex are required.

The overall facility design has progressed well given the available resources. The transmission and beam emittance has been estimated across the facility. Further development of the lattice design may reveal new issues, but also make possible a global optimisation for cost, power and performance. Some technical issues have been uncovered. None of the issues have impacted the concept feasibility although in some areas the performance relative to target parameters may be degraded. Innovative approaches have enabled the IMCC to exceed target parameters in other areas. **Overall we are convinced that the target luminosity is achievable.** If the target luminosity can be met **IMCC considers that we have a significant contingency in luminosity in hand.**

The power consumption for CERN implementations at 3.2 and 7.6 TeV and the 10 TeV site-independent design are about 117 MW, 182 MW, and 201 MW, respectively.

5 Timeline and R&D plan

Fig. 5: Technically limited timeline for the initial muon collider stage, assuming a firm commitment to implement the project as soon as possible after the High-Luminosity LHC. The timeline of the project phases beyond the planned 10 years of R&D are affected by the siting choice and detailed planning by the host laboratory.

A roadmap towards a muon collider must remain flexible, and is an important part of a diverse international research programme in particle physics. New results, from the HL-LHC or non-accelerator based experiments, and potentially also lower energy experiments, might change the desired parameters for a future muon collider. Societal changes and priorities might also influence resource availability and hence timelines for investments in basic science as needed for future colliders. The potential of a muon collider to reach around 10 TeV parton-parton collisions with high luminosity makes it an exciting opportunity for the near and more distant future.

IMCC proposes a comprehensive R&D programme to reach the maturity required to initiate the approval process. The programme requires approximately 300 MCHF material budget and about 1800 FTEy of personnel for the accelerator and about 20 MCHF and 900 FTEy for detectors. With timely funding, the programme spans about 10 years. This would enable a first muon collider stage with a start

of operation around 2050. It could thus be the next flagship project in Europe in case no Higgs factory is realised at CERN. A slightly longer timescale is envisaged for an implementation in the U.S. taking into account budget constraints.

The first phase of the R&D programme contains completion of a start-to-end facility design. It also includes hardware development of components that drive the overall timeline for the collider such as the superconducting magnets and the muon cooling technology. After this phase a ramp-up of resources will enable a more detailed facility design to prepare for the start of the decision process. This process could start in 2036 and allow investing into industrialisation of the components before project construction approval. The proposed technically limited timeline, shown in Figure 5, is feasible, contingent on the strong commitment from the community and the funding agencies to realise a muon collider at the earliest possible time.

The proposed R&D plan will achieve the following:

- Further development of the **detector** will optimise the performance and minimise the impact of beam induced background.
- The **muon cooling technology** demonstration programme will develop this novel technology. It will develop the components such as the HTS solenoids, the cavities and the absorbers. Test of a full cooling cell with RF power will allow verification of the integrated performance. The demonstrator facility will test several of the cooling cells with beam to demonstrate the technology.
- An intense programme will establish the **superconducting magnet** performance through the construction and test of models and prototypes. It will focus in particular on HTS solenoids for the muon production target and the muon cooling. These have strong synergy with applications in society such as fusion reactors. A model of the collider ring dipoles will also be constructed and establish the field at large aperture.
- A **start-to-end model** of the collider. The completion of the lattice design along the whole complex and its optimisation will guide the component development. The development of simulation tools that include the relevant beam physics, such as collective effects and imperfections as well as the relevant mitigation techniques, will enable robust luminosity predictions. A study of the machine availability will establish the integrated luminosity performance and guide component and accelerator design.
- Experiments in combination with further design work will verify the **target** robustness.
- Conceptual designs of the superconducting and normal-conducting **cavities** along the whole complex. Experimental verification of the performance limits will allow to optimise the complex design. In particular, the construction of an infrastructure to test RF in a high magnet field will enable experimental optimisation and verification of the normal-conducting muon cooling RF.
- The development of high-power, high-efficiency **klystrons** will be instrumental for the muon cooling cell test and enable cost effective design.
- The performance of the **fast-ramping magnet systems and power converter** for the Rapid-Cycling Synchrotrons (RCS) will be demonstrated.
- **Site and environmental impact studies**, including civil engineering, will allow optimisation for power consumption and material usage as well as minimising the impact of the machine for the local environment.
- An **overall optimisation** of the complex for cost, power consumption and risk will be performed and is particularly essential since we cannot base ourselves on experience with previous similar projects. This optimisation will also cross the boundaries between the different systems.

It will also be important to explore promising alternatives to the current baseline, e.g. the use of a Fixed-Field Accelerator (FFA) in the proton complex to reduce the linac energy and cost.

6 Synergies

Particle physics and the associated accelerator and detector development have made important contributions to society; both in training of young people and in developing technologies.

Many young people have developed their scientific and technical skills in the field; they also learned to work in fully international collaborations. Because the muon collider is a novel concept it opens opportunities for young researchers to make original contributions to the development that are much harder to make in long-established design approaches.

The muon collider needs technologies in several areas that differ from other colliders. High-field solenoids are a prime example. In the past low-temperature superconductors such as the very mature NbTi and still developing Nb₃Sn were the technologies of choice for accelerators and most other applications. Now HTS are becoming an important technology. In particular, they are of interest for fusion reactors, that have similar requirements to the one for the muon collider target solenoid. Highly-efficient superconducting motors and power generators, e.g., for off-shore windmills, also have strong synergy. Other relevant areas are life and material sciences; in particular, applications exist for nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). In addition synergy exists with magnets for neutron spectroscopy, physics detectors and magnets for other particle colliders, such as hadron colliders.

The muon production target is synergetic with neutron spallation sources targets and neutrino targets, in particular the alternative liquid metal concept.

The muon collider RF power sources have synergy with other developments of high-efficiency klystrons and superconducting cavities. Some RF systems need to work in high magnetic fields, an issue that also exists in some fusion reactor designs.

The test facility and the collider itself require a high power proton source to produce muon beams of unprecedented intensity and brightness and experimental conditions not available in any other facility. This allows sharing technology and potentially even facilities. Neutron spallation sources such as SNS and ESS are major examples; other examples are neutrino facilities, such as NuSTORM, lepton flavour violation experiments, such as mu2e and COMET and low-energy muon beam facilities used for materials science.

7 Conclusion

The formation of IMCC has enabled important progress on the muon collider design and technologies, greatly increasing confidence in the concept. Investment in an experimental programme for the technologies is now essential for further progress. Demonstrating key technologies for muon cooling—such as HTS solenoids, RF cavities, klystrons, absorbers and their integration into cooling cells—will advance the novel aspects of the design. Additionally, the development of other critical technologies, including fast-ramping magnet systems, high-field superconducting dipoles, high-power target and superconducting RF technology, will optimise collider performance. The technology development has strong synergies with other projects, such as FCC-hh, as well as applications with significant societal impact, such as fusion reactors. Increasing effort on the start-to-end design will enable robust predictions of luminosity performance and availability of the collider, optimise cost, power consumption, and risk, and guide the continued development of technologies.

Global interest in the muon collider as a path to 10 TeV parton-parton collisions is growing, with CERN and Fermilab currently being considered as potential sites. Initial exploration indicates that a muon collider could be implemented at CERN, reusing the SPS and LHC tunnels. The corresponding technically limited timeline indicates that a first collider stage could be available by around 2050. Following HL-LHC or a potential fast Higgs factory, the muon collider could thus become Europe's next flagship project.

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Addendum to: The Muon Collider

Input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics – 2026 update

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Input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics - 2026 update

The International Muon Collider Collaboration

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Abstract

Muons offer a unique opportunity to build a compact high-energy electroweak collider at the 10 TeV scale. A Muon Collider enables direct access to the underlying simplicity of the Standard Model and unparalleled reach beyond it. It will be a paradigm-shifting tool for particle physics representing the first collider to combine the high-energy reach of a proton collider and the high precision of an electron-positron collider, yielding a physics potential significantly greater than the sum of its individual parts. A high-energy muon collider is the natural next step in the exploration of fundamental physics after the HL-LHC and a natural complement to a future low-energy Higgs factory. Such a facility would significantly broaden the scope of particle colliders, engaging the many frontiers of the high energy community.

The last European Strategy for Particle Physics Update and later the Particle Physics Project Prioritisation Panel in the US requested a study of the muon collider, which is being carried on by the International Muon Collider Collaboration.

In this document, we directly address the questions listed in the guidelines for inputs for the large-scale projects by the European Strategy Secretariat.

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1 Stages and parameters

1.a The main stages of the project and the key scientific goals of each

IMCC is studying a site independent collider implementation to reach around 10 TeV collision energies. It is also studying site specific options that take advantage of existing infrastructure and limitations at CERN and FNAL.

At CERN, IMCC has developed a solution that reuses existing tunnels with an initial stage having 3.2 TeV centre-of-mass energy followed by an upgrade to 7.6 TeV centre-of-mass energy. Acceleration for 3.2 TeV would be achieved using a sequence of one Rapid Cycling Synchrotron in the SPS tunnel and a further RCS in the HL-LHC tunnel. The beam would be extracted to a collider ring. A further RCS would be installed in the HL-LHC tunnel to enable acceleration for 7.6 TeV. The beam would then be extracted to a collider ring.

IMCC considers that an initial lower energy collider can produce physics results earlier. A 3.2 TeV stage would enable an exquisite physics programme that explores collisions at the highest energy conceived for any lepton-antilepton collider. It would offer the first significant step beyond the HL-LHC in understanding the Higgs potential as well as testing Dark Matter candidates. The upgrade to 7.6 TeV would extend our understanding of EWSB even further allowing a differential test of EW restoration. Other energies, such as 125 GeV for resonant Higgs production and energies beyond 10 TeV have not been studied but are possible. A resonant Higgs factory may be important if no other low-energy Higgs factory were realised.

Table 1.a: Selected muon collider energy stages and corresponding luminosity ranges (depending on the collider ring and magnet technology circumference).

Parameter	Symbol	unit	Site independent		CERN	
			Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 1	Stage 2
Centre-of-mass energy	E_{cm}	TeV	3	10	3.2	7.6
Target integrated luminosity	$\int \mathcal{L}_{\text{target}}$	ab^{-1}	1	10	1	10
Estimated luminosity	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{estimated}}$	$10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.8	17.5	0.9–2.0	7.9–10.1
Collider dipole technology			Nb ₃ Sn	HTS	NbTi or Nb ₃ Sn	Nb ₃ Sn or HTS

1.b For each stage, the main technical parameters

IMCC is focusing on a collider that reaches around 10 TeV centre-of-mass energy. It also considers that a staged implementation can deliver physics earlier. The project has been studied for implementation at CERN and FNAL and for a site-independent implementation, assuming that no infrastructure can be reused. Four possible implementations are described here:

- A CERN-specific implementation with an initial 3.2 TeV stage followed by a 7.6 TeV stage where the collider ring is reused with a magnet upgrade.
- A CERN-specific implementation with an initial 3.2 TeV stage followed by a 7.6 TeV stage where a bespoke collider ring is used for each stage.
- A site independent option with an initial 3 TeV stage followed by a 10 TeV stage.
- A site independent option with an initial 10 TeV stage followed by a higher luminosity 10 TeV stage.

The different options are listed in tables 1.b and 1.c.

The collider dipole technology is a key bounding parameter. IMCC expects that HTS collider ring dipoles will not be available for a next-generation collider in 2050. Higher dipole fields would enable shorter collider rings and yield higher luminosity. The available magnet technology constrains the available dipole field and consequently impacts on the staging scenarios.

The implementation at CERN can use the SPS tunnel to house one RCS and the LHC tunnel to house two RCSs. This allows to reach a collision energy of 7.6 TeV with the technology studied for the site-independent scenario; to be developed fast-ramping HTS magnets in the final RCS might increase this energy. A natural maximum staging energy for this implementation would be 3.2 TeV since the final energy of the first RCS in the LHC tunnel is 1.6 TeV.

Two example implementations for CERN are presented in table 1.c. The first uses the strongest dipole field available at the time and the smallest collider ring tunnel circumference for each stage and yields highest luminosity. The second has the lowest luminosity of the range of possible implementations. It uses the same 11 km collider ring tunnel for both stages. This implementation could reach 7.6 TeV with Nb₃Sn dipoles and 3.2 TeV with established NbTi technology.

For the site independent implementation two staging scenarios are considered, see table 1.b. They are based on the assumption that Nb₃Sn dipoles can be available for operation by 2050 but high-field HTS dipoles will be available only later. The first, energy staging, scenario consists of a 3 TeV stage, followed by a 10 TeV stage. The first stage uses three RCS and a 4.5 km-long collider with Nb₃Sn dipoles. The second stage adds an additional RCS and uses a new 11.4 km collider ring with HTS dipoles. The second, luminosity staging, scenario implements 10 TeV collider already in the first stage. This requires to use Nb₃Sn collider ring magnets and hence a longer tunnel. Later the luminosity can be upgraded with better interaction region magnets, similar to HL-LHC.

1.c The number of independent experimental activities and the number of scientists expected to be engaged in each.

The muon collider can naturally provide beams to up to two interaction points, with no loss of delivered luminosity compared to a single interaction point. In addition, it is expected to exploit the bright neutrino beams produced in the straight sections leading to the interaction points with dedicated stand-alone experimental facilities, located along the neutrino beam path. Two such facilities could be supported for each interaction point on the collider ring. Furthermore, a muon beam dump facility is being considered, targeting dark sector models. A suitably designed proton driver could enable a non-collider physics programme similar to the existing one at CERN. In particular, the Proton Synchrotron Booster and the Proton Synchrotron could continue to operate; continued operation of the SPS or its replacement with the first RCS is likely possible. The high-power proton complex for the muon production could enable additional opportunities.

It is expected to instrument each of the interaction points located on the collider ring with general purpose particle physics experiments. Because of the breadth of the muon collider physics programme, and because of the complexity of the experimental apparatus, each experiment should require the engagement of a community with a size comparable to ATLAS, CMS, or general purpose detectors at future hadron colliders. Based on the ATLAS and CMS community size, this would likely correspond to about 6000 scientists. Each dedicated neutrino experiment will engage a community of up to several hundred scientists. The muon beam dump facility, if realized, can also attract about a hundred independent scientists. A suitably designed proton driver could support a programme similar to the existing CERN non-collider physics programme.

Table 1.b: Tentative target parameters for a site independent muon collider at different energies if target performances are achieved. Scenario 1 corresponds to Energy Staging, and Scenario 2 corresponds to Luminosity Staging.

Site independent muon collider parameters						
Parameter	Symbol	unit	Energy staging		Luminosity staging	
			Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 1	Stage 2
Centre-of-mass energy	E_{cm}	TeV	3	10	10	10
Target integrated luminosity	$\int \mathcal{L}_{\text{target}}$	ab^{-1}	1	10	10	
Estimated luminosity	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{estimated}}$	$10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	1.8	17.5	4 (tbc)	13.8
Collider circumference	C_{coll}	km	4.5	11.4	15	15
Collider arc peak field	B_{arc}	T	11	14	11	11
Collider dipole technology			Nb ₃ Sn	HTS	Nb ₃ Sn	Nb ₃ Sn
Luminosity lifetime	N_{turn}	turns	1039	1363	1039	1039
Muons/bunch	N	10^{12}	2.2	1.8	1.8	1.8
Repetition rate	f_{r}	Hz	5	5	5	5
Beam power	P_{coll}	MW	5.3	14.4	14.4	14.4
RMS longitudinal emittance	ε_{\parallel}	eVs	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
Norm. RMS transv. emittance	ε_{\perp}	μm	25	25	25	25
IP bunch length	σ_z	mm	5	1.5	5 (tbc)	1.5
IP betafunctor	β	mm	5	1.5	5 (tbc)	1.5
IP beam size	σ	μm	3	0.9	1.6	0.9
Protons on target/bunch	N_{p}	10^{14}	5	5	5	5
Protons energy on target	E_{p}	GeV	5	5	5	5

Table 1.c: Examples of tentative target parameters for a CERN implementation of the muon collider, reusing the SPS and LHC tunnels. Scenario 1 uses a 11 km tunnel for both stages, Scenario 2 uses optimal tunnel circumferences; the corresponding civil engineering studies remain to be performed.

CERN-specific muon collider parameters						
Parameter	Symbol	unit	Scenario 1		Scenario 2	
			Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 1	Stage 2
Centre-of-mass energy	E_{cm}	TeV	3.2	7.6	3.2	7.6
Target integrated luminosity	$\int \mathcal{L}_{\text{target}}$	ab^{-1}	1	10	1	10
Estimated luminosity	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{estimated}}$	$10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	0.9	7.9	2.0	10.1
Collider circumference	C_{coll}	km	11	11	4.8	8.7
Collider arc peak field	B_{arc}	T	4.8	11	11	14
Collider dipole technology			NbTi	Nb ₃ Sn or HTS	Nb ₃ Sn	HTS
Muons/bunch	N	10^{12}	2.2	1.8	2.2	1.8
Beam power	P_{coll}	MW	5.6	10.9	5.6	10.9
IP bunch length	σ_z	mm	4.7	2	4.7	2
IP betafunctor	β	mm	4.7	2	4.7	2
IP beam size	σ	μm	2.8	1.2	2.8	1.2

2 Timeline

2.a The technically-limited timeline for construction of each stage

The muon collider concept requires significant R&D to achieve the maturity level needed for implementation. The timeline is largely driven by the progress of the R&D programme.

In Europe, hosting the collider is being considered either following a Higgs factory or as the next flagship project after the HL-LHC. In the United States, there is strong interest in hosting the collider to reassert leadership at the high-energy frontier. To guide the definition of the R&D programme, an ambitious technically limited timeline has been explored together by European and US experts. This scenario assumes a firm commitment to implementing a muon collider in Europe as soon as possible after the HL-LHC, with the goal of beginning operation around 2050 (see Figure 2.a). It prioritizes reuse of existing CERN infrastructure to minimize civil engineering costs and limits the collider’s center-of-mass energy to approximately 3 TeV, consistent with realistic expectations for the development of high-field HTS dipole magnets.

The initial phase of the project focuses on advancing the design and the required technologies to a level that allows the feasibility of a muon collider to be demonstrated with confidence. The expected deliverables of this phase are listed in Table 5.b. The estimated resource requirements for this phase are approximately 320 million CHF in materials and 2700 full-time equivalent years (FTEy) in personnel, including 20 million CHF and 900 FTEy allocated to detector development. This phase is expected to last a minimum of 10 years.

Once feasibility has been established, the project preparation phase can begin, requiring at least five years. Although detailed resource estimates for this stage are not yet available, they are expected to exceed those of the initial phase. The subsequent construction phase would then require a minimum of nine years. The plan will have to be re-evaluated if the required resources are not available and/or if other considerations lead to a more stretched timeline for the implementation at CERN. The R&D timelines underpinning the overall timeline are given in 5.b and 5.c.

The U.S. community similarly targets operation in the early 2050s, with a focus on a single-stage 10 TeV collider. This timeline differs slightly in length and structure from the European plan, i.e. requiring 17 years to prepare a Technical Design Report, compared to 15 years in the European scenario.

At present, R&D progress is limited by available resources, both in Europe and particularly in the U.S., where organizational structures are still being established. It is therefore important to increase the design effort in order to complete a start-to-end design of the collider and to launch the technology R&D that has the strongest impact on the timeline. IMCC plans to review the Roadmap in 2028, following the results of the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU) and the subsequent mid-term review panel recommended by the P5 report. At that point, a decision can be made on the location of the demonstrator facility and it could be approved.

Fig. 2.a: Technically limited timeline for the initial muon collider stage, assuming a firm commitment to implement the project as soon as possible after the High-Luminosity LHC. The timeline of the project phases beyond the planned 10 years of R&D are affected by the siting choice and detailed planning by the host laboratory.

2.b The anticipated operational (running) time at each stage, and the expected operational duty cycle

No specific study has been performed to optimise the running time at each energy. Initial integrated luminosity goals have been set as 1 ab^{-1} and 10 ab^{-1} for 3 and 10 TeV. Operation time at the high energy is of the order of at least 10 years. For a 3 TeV stage, it will depend on the funding of the second stage and the technology development for the collider ring dipoles. A period of approximately 10 years of operation appears as a reasonable prediction.

The operation time per year is expected to be similar to other proposed projects, such as CLIC, and be in the range of $1 - 1.2 \times 10^7$ s per year. Detailed studies will establish the margins and redundancies that are required to reach the necessary availability in the 70-80% range and the impact that this has on the cost.

3 Resource requirements

3.a The capital cost of each stage in 2024 CHF

The capital cost range is provided for the CERN scenario as compared to a Green Field realization in Figure 3.a

Fig. 3.a: The cost range is presented for the scenario of energy staging of the Muon Collider facility as compared to the Green Field realization. The cost for each stage represents the cost for a complete facility. The darkest part of the colour band identifies the most probable values, while the lighter sides of the band materialize the extension of the calculated uncertainty. Red markers show the position of the most probable value.

The Snowmass 2021 Collider Implementation Task Force [1] proposed a general formula for estimating the labour needed for construction:

$$\text{Explicit Labour} = 15.7 \cdot (\text{Value})^{0.75}, \quad (3.a)$$

with Explicit Labour in FTE-years and Value in MCHF of 2010. This indicates that a CERN implementation requires around 18500 and 24000 FTE-years for 3.2 TeV and 7.6 TeV, respectively. An important part of these could be covered outside CERN, for in-kind deliverables.

3.b The annual cost of operations of each stage

The annual cost of operation is calculated on the basis of the investment cost and by considering the estimated needs in terms of spare parts. The following percentages are considered:

- 1% calculated for RF cavities, cryostats, magnets.
- 3% calculated for RF power and power converters.
- 5% calculated for CFS and cryogenics.

The replacement / operation cost will then be most likely around 200 MCHF for the low energy stage at 3.2 TeV and around 250 MCHF for the stage at 7.6 TeV.

In addition one has to consider the cost of energy for operation. In 4.a the estimated energy consumption is estimated for the different states of the machine and it is shown to be in the range of 0.78 - 1.12 TWh. The associated cost will then depend on the negotiated price of energy at that moment. A

contract for the supply of energy for the LHC Run 4 has not been signed yet at the day of writing, for example, but we know that from 2026 CERN will make the transition from the ARENH price mechanism provided by the French supplier to market prices, with the associated uncertainty. It is generally assumed a cost of 80 CHF/MWh for energy as of today, which would imply an operation cost of about 90 MCHF for the 7.6 TeV stage.

3.c The human resources (in FTE) needed to deliver or operate each stage over its lifetime, expressed as an annual profile

The resources for operating the muon collider facility in the scenario of a CERN installation are expected to be very similar to those that are presently necessary for operating the CERN accelerator complex, however a detailed study would certainly be required. A detailed study performed by the ILC, which was also analyzed in the CLIC context, showed a need of 640 FTE. In the case of the muon collider, one can introduce some uncertainty in the estimate, also related to the operation of some innovative systems, like the long cooling channel, the target area for the muon production and the collider SC magnets in the presence of a high radiation load, and expect a need ranging between 700 to 900 FTE.

3.d Commentary on the basis-of-estimate of the resource requirements

At the time when the estimate is performed, the Muon Collider design is still in a pre-CDR stage, where the architecture has been developed to a certain level of detail and the main beam parameters are known with some accuracy, but still several options exist that may steer the project into different directions, with considerable impact on the final cost. For these reasons, the estimate is presented in the form of a cost range, which is justified partly by the level of maturity of the chosen technologies and partly due to the extrapolation of the cost information from other projects and studies.

An initial choice was made to consider the installation on the CERN site as a possible first configuration for the realisation of the Muon Collider, by also assuming that it would make the best use of the existing tunnels and technical infrastructure. That would certainly keep the environmental impact related to the civil engineering realisations on the low side, in spite of some initial limitations to the performance reach of the facility that may follow from this choice. The successive analysis looks into the cost variance introduced by the adoption of beyond state-of-the-art technologies that will push the overall performance and by configuration options that will allow the complex to deploy its full potential.

A project breakdown structure (PBS) was developed and for each area of the facility a few systems could be identified as the major contributors to the overall cost. The PBS considers four levels of complexity providing increasing detail starting from the Machine Sector down to Facility, System and Component. Work package leaders in charge of different technological areas were asked to provide their estimates of cost for equipment considered as the cost drivers, together with the level of maturity for the specific technology. The main cost drivers are represented by the civil engineering, the general technical infrastructure, the cryogenic system, the magnet system with power converters and by the RF system with the RF power generation. The cost of these main items is mostly estimated with a bottom-up approach by contacting recognised experts in the field and in some cases by soliciting cost estimates from industrial partners. Other sources of cost are extrapolated from previous projects.

The analysis presents the cost for each stage as a complete facility, rather than evaluating the incremental cost from one stage to the next, due to the significant error margin that affects any cost estimate at the moment. This kind of estimate will become possible after that the necessary R&D will have been produced and more accurate estimates will become possible.

Having considered the level of maturity of the project, the analysis aims at obtaining a rough order of magnitude (ROM) estimate for the different stages that have been considered, with a level of precision that combines Class IV and Class V estimates for different areas of the project. For the same reason cost uncertainties take into account technical uncertainties only and do not consider purchase uncertainties.

4 Environmental impact

4.a The peak (MW) and integrated (TWh) energy consumption during operation of each stage

The power consumption has been estimated for the two energy stages at CERN and it is summarized in Table 4.b together with the yearly energy consumption. In order to obtain the energy consumption a possible scheme for the operation time has been adopted as presented in Table 4.a with an assumed uptime efficiency of 77.5%. The stand-by state that has been used for the energy calculations corresponds to a state of accelerators when only cryogenics, magnets and the cooling and ventilation systems are powered and running.

Table 4.a: Muon Collider complex yearly operation time.

	Days
Operation	165
Luminosity	115.5
Technical stops	15
Machine development	20
Commissioning	40
YETS	125
	Hours
Operation	4509
Stand-by	1251
Off	3000

Table 4.b: Power and Energy consumption for the Muon Collider energy stages in the CERN scenario.

	Unit	3.2 TeV	7.6 TeV
Operation power	MW	117	182
Energy consumption	TWh	0.53	0.82
Stand-by power	MW	73	111
Energy consumption	TWh	0.09	0.14
Off state power	MW	58	69
Energy consumption	TWh	0.17	0.21
Yearly energy consumption	TWh	0.8	1.2

The facility wall-plug power requirement was estimated based on the sum of the estimated power consumption of each individual component. The estimate of power consumption for RF cavities was based on operation of known RF cavities and sources, including requirements for cooling of superconducting cavities. Power losses arising from operation of the pulsed normal conducting magnets was estimated based on comparison of calculation validated across three different codes and combined with loss estimates of both unipolar and bipolar pulsed resonance circuits as appropriate. All power estimates took advantage of the low duty factor required for the muon collider compared to other facilities. Additional heat load induced by the beam to RF cryostats in the RCSs was tentatively included into the operation power budget. In a worst case scenario, this power is of the order of 12 MW for the 3.2 TeV stage and up to 29 MW for the 7.6 TeV case. Collimation of the losses before and after the cavities will reduce the cooling requirements. We assume that the actual power is one third of the pessimistic case. However, the design and detailed study remains to be done. Further details of the estimated wall-plug power requirement of individual components may be found in Chapter 6 of Ref. [2].

4.b The integrated carbon-equivalent energy cost of construction

A life-cycle assessment of the ILC and CLIC accelerator facilities performed by ARUP to evaluate their holistic global warming potential (GWP), has so far provided the most detailed environmental impact analysis of construction. The components of construction are divided into classes: raw material supply, material transport, material manufacture, material transport to work site, and construction process. These are labelled A1 through A5, where A1-A3 are grouped as materials emissions and A4-A5 are grouped as transport and construction process emissions. The approximate construction GWP for the main tunnels are 6.38 kton CO₂e/km for CLIC (5.6m diameter) and 7.34 kton CO₂e /km for ILC (9.5m diameter); the Muon Collider tunnel design is similar to that of CLIC, so 6.38 kton CO₂e/km is used here for the calculation of emissions.

While a comprehensive civil engineering report is unavailable for the Muon Collider, we estimate the concrete required for access shafts, alcoves, caverns, klystron galleries, etc. to contribute an additional 30% of emissions, similar to what is anticipated for other colliders. The analysis indicates that the A4-A5 components constitute 20% for CLIC and 15% for ILC. In the absence of equivalent life cycle assessment analysis for the Muon Collider, we account for the A4-A5 contributions as an additional 25%. For a greenfield site, a 3 TeV or 10 TeV Muon Collider would require approximately 30 km and 70 km of tunnels, respectively. However, a site reusing existing infrastructure such as CERN for 7.6 TeV center of mass would only need 15 km of tunnels primarily limited to the muon source, cooling channel and the collider ring. For these three cases the emissions in kton CO₂e is on the order of 700, 300 and 150 for decreasing tunnel length, including A1-A5 contributions as described above.

4.c Any other significant expected environmental impacts

Tentative studies indicate the potential for the neutrino flux to have a negligible impact on the environment, similar to LHC. Initial studies focus on two main challenges:

- The experiments as well as beam injection and extraction are placed in straight insertions. Along the projection of these straights, the neutrino flux can be quite high. For CERN a first orientation of the collider has been identified whereby the neutrino flux emerges in two non-built-up spots in the Jura mountains, which would allow to fence the area and place experiments as appropriate. The other exit points would be in the Mediterranean Sea. Potential other orientations remain to be explored.
- The flux from the arcs is mitigated with a mover system. The system will avoid significant localised neutrino flux by systematically changing the beam angle between -1 mrad and $+1$ mrad. If applied in the horizontal and vertical plane, this would yield a negligible neutrino flux at the surface. Detailed studies of the impact of the system on the beam remain to be performed.

Further optimisation and expansion of the studies to the full complex are required.

5 Technology and delivery

5.a The key technologies needed for delivery that are still under development in 2024, and the targeted performance parameters of each development

By 2036-37, the muon collider project aims to achieve readiness for a staged implementation, requiring R&D resources around 300 MCHF and 1800 FTE-years for the accelerator and 20 MCHF and 900 FTE-years for the detector between 2026 and 2036. A breakdown of the resources is provided in Table 5.a.

Year	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
Accelerator Design and Technologies										
Material (MCHF)	1.6	3.2	4.8	6.4	9.6	10.8	12.0	12.0	12.0	12.0
FTE	47.1	60.6	75.0	85.0	100.0	120.0	150.0	174.6	177.2	185.1
Demonstrator										
Material (MCHF)	0.6	2.2	3.9	5.4	7.8	15.1	25.9	32.4	31.8	12.6
FTE	9.5	11.0	12.5	29.2	29.7	30.5	25.5	27.7	26.7	25.5
Detector										
Material (MCHF)	0.5	1.1	1.6	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.6	3.1	3.1
FTE	23.4	46.5	70.0	93.0	93.0	93.0	93.0	116.4	139.5	139.5
Magnets										
Material (MCHF)	3.0	4.9	10.1	10.0	11.0	13.4	11.7	7.2	6.6	4.7
FTE	23.3	28.4	36.4	40.9	44.3	47.1	46.2	37.7	36.1	29.4
TOTALS										
Material (MCHF)	5.7	11.4	20.3	23.9	30.6	41.4	51.7	54.2	53.5	32.4
FTE	103.3	146.5	194.0	248.1	267.0	290.6	314.8	356.3	379.4	379.6

Table 5.a: Summary of R&D resources, divided by area, over a ten year period. Personnel is given as average Full Time Equivalent (FTE), where students count as 50% FTE. Material is given in millions of CHF (MCHF). The total is the sum of the four areas.

This R&D investment would enable a first operational stage around 2050. Key milestones include construction and testing of essential magnets and demonstrating cooling technology, both of which drive the schedule. Readiness requires a mature baseline design, TRL 6+ technologies, comprehensive site and environmental studies, and advanced cost, power, and schedule assessments. Further progress is also needed in physics and detector studies. Part III of the supplementary report contains a detailed description of the R&D [2]. The main elements for the accelerator design are listed in Table 5.b and are grouped as follows:

- **Magnet technology developments:** HTS solenoids for muon production and cooling; and collider ring dipoles and fast-ramping magnet systems.
- **RF technologies:** components such as klystrons; cavities working in high magnetic field and with high beam loading; and test infrastructure.
- **Muon cooling technology:** the technologies for muon cooling and their integration into the 6D cooling and the final cooling system.
- **Design and technologies:** study of key design challenges, including collider modelling; lattice optimization; advanced simulations; site impact studies to balance cost, efficiency, and risk; and technical developments as target, RF and MDI.
- **The muon cooling demonstration programme:** integration and test of cooling technologies; performance verification; and development of key components like HTS solenoids and RF systems.
- **Detector R&D priorities:** simulation; technology; and software to enhance physics output while reducing beam-induced backgrounds, which are not included in the table.

Table 5.b: Key deliverables of the proposed R&D programme.

Technologies	Deliverables	Key parameters and goals
Magnets		
Target solenoid	Develop conductor, winding and magnet technology	1 m inner / 2.3 m outer diameters, 1.4 m length, 20 T at 20 K
Split 6D cooling solenoid	Demonstration of solenoid with cell integration	510 mm bore, gap 200 mm, 7 T at 20 K
Final cooling solenoid	Build and test HTS prototype	50 mm bore, 15 cm length, 40 T at 4 K
Fast-ramping magnet system	Prototype magnet string and power converter	30 mm x 100 mm, 1.8 T, 3.3 T/s
LTS collider dipole	Demonstrate Nb ₃ Sn collider dipole	160 mm diameter, 11 T, 4.5 K, 5 m long
HTS RCS dipole	Demonstrate RCS HTS dipole	30 mm x 100 mm, 10 T, 20 K, 1 m long
HTS collider dipole	Demonstrate HTS collider dipole	140 mm diameter, 14 T, 20 K, 1 m long
HTS collider quadrupole	Demonstrate HTS IR quadrupole	140 mm diameter, 300T/m, 4.5K, 1m long
Radiofrequency		
Muon cooling RF cavities	Design, build and test RF cavities	352 MHz and 704 MHz in 10 T field
Klystron prototype	Design/build with Industry 704 MHz (and later 352 MHz) klystron	20 MW peak power, 704 MHz / 352 MHz
RF test stands	Assess cavity breakdown rate in magnetic field	20-32 MV/m, 704 MHz–3 GHz cavities in 7–10 T
SCRF cavities	Design SRF cavities, FPC and HOM couplers, fast tuners, cryomodules	352 MHz, 1056 MHz, 1.3 GHz, 1 MW peak power (FPC)
Muon Cooling		
First 6D cooling cell	Build and test first cooling cell	
5-cell module	Build and test first 5-cell cooling module	
Cooling demonstrator	Design and build cooling demonstrator facility	Infrastructure to test cooling modules with muon beam
Final cooling absorber	Experimental determination of final cooling absorber limit	3×10^{12} muons, 22.5 μ m emittance, 40 T field
Design & Other Technologies		
Neutrino flux mover system	Protoype components and tests as needed	Range to reach O(\pm 1mradian)
Beam Instrumentation	Instrumentation component designs	Protoype components and tests as needed
Target Studies	Target design and test of relevant components	0.4 MJ/pulse, 5 Hz
Start-to-End Facility Design	A start-to-end model of the machine consistent with realistic performance specifications	Lattice designs of all beamlines, simulation codes with relevant beam physics, tuning and feedback procedures

5.b The critical path for technology development or design

The IMCC has identified several items that are critical for delivery of the muon collider on a next-generation time scale.

- The **Demonstration of an integrated rectilinear cooling module** is necessary in order to verify that the technology can be realised and to inform a decision making process on the muon collider facility at the conceptual design stage. The proposed cooling cells are very compact so that integration of equipment poses significant challenges in thermal and force management which must be verified in hardware. Delivery of a beam test will follow to inform the technical design and eventual operation of the facility. As part of the Demonstration of Cooling, a **prerequisite RF Test Programme** is required to demonstrate that the proposed RF gradients are achievable even in the presence of strong magnetic fields. The cooling system RF gradient requirement is about 25% lower than that achieved in a test programme in the US in relevant conditions but IMCC still considers this an important risk. Higher gradients would improve performance.
- Several critical **magnet** technologies require advanced prototypes to be sure that the design criteria can be met, in particular for the high-field HTS solenoids required for muon production and cooling which have fields up to 25% higher than currently available solenoids. Delivery of solenoids having capabilities beyond those proposed would improve the performance.
- A **start-to-end design of the facility** is required to improve the reliability of the existing power, cost and performance estimate in order to approve the muon collider project. Several design areas rely on previous studies which are not fully integrated and carry risks which must be mitigated. A start-to-end design would improve understanding of the relative trade-off between different sub-systems which may yield an improvement in power, cost or performance.
- The high-energy muon collider **detectors** must be optimized for physics in the challenging environment created by machine-induced backgrounds. Most detector components must simultaneously optimize position resolution, timing capability, radiation hardness, data transmission, and on-detector background rejection, all while maintaining low mass and low power consumption. Research and development must focus on developing the necessary detector technologies, tools, and crucial expertise to construct state-of-the-art detectors for this future machine.

The estimated timeline is shown in Figure 2.a. The timeline for the Demonstrator is shown in Figure 5.a and for the magnet development in Figure 5.b.

5.c A concise assessment of the key technical risks to the delivery of the project

The proposed R&D program is designed to address the key risks in delivering collision energy and luminosity as well as good experimental conditions and site options within an appropriate cost and time envelope. Table 5.a details the key components and the target performances when they are not based on already achieved values. Risk to each of these parameters may be mitigated in the following ways:

- **Siting:** neutrinos arising from muon decay may create a weak neutron shower near to the surface. Neutrinos may arise from decay of muons in the straight sections near the interaction point or the arcs. An implementation has been identified that mitigates the neutrino flux risk from the interaction point straights. Neutrinos emerge in two non-built-up sites in the Jura mountains and Mediterranean sea, which could provide an ideal location for neutrino physics experiments. In the arcs a system of movers will change the beam angle between -1 mrad and +1 mrad in order to make a negligible impact, consistent with the equivalent impact from operation of the LHC. IMCC must demonstrate that the movers can operate remaining within alignment constraints. As the project matures, appropriate permitting and consents must be established for the proposed remote sites.
- **Experimental Conditions:** Muon decay products can impinge on the detectors creating electromagnetic showers that lead to Beam-Induced Background. Tungsten masks protect the detector

Fig. 5.a: Technically limited timeline for the Muon Cooling Demonstrator programme, including the prerequisite RF R&D.

Fig. 5.b: Technically limited timeline for the Muon Magnet programme.

from the BIB and detector components with high time and space resolution further reduce this impact. Dedicated studies indicate that the radiation in the detector region is roughly similar to HL-LHC, even if not uniformly distributed.

- **Integrated Design:** IMCC has designed key components but a number of other components have not yet been designed. Sufficient accelerator physics resources are required to complete and optimise the lattice design, which can profit from several iterations in difficult cases, and to guide the technology development. The mitigation of collective effects and imperfections along the whole

chain is essential to avoid a bottleneck for the bunch charge or emittance growth; an assessment of the component availability and the impact on integrated luminosity is essential. The start-to-end model presents an opportunity; optimisation may yield performance improvements and allows trade-offs between different systems and technologies to be made. It can also uncover risk, which must be managed by further design work.

- **Muon Cooling:** The muon cooling system requires close integration of absorbers, magnets and RF cavities. Large forces between neighbouring magnets must be managed while allowing sufficient space for services to RF cavities. RF cavities must operate at high gradients despite the intense solenoid fields. The IMCC has developed a full engineering design of a typical cooling cell that adequately manages the forces. Previous experiments have demonstrated RF gradients that are 25 % higher than the requirements for the cooling system, but the response to parameters (frequency, magnetic field, etc) has not been fully characterised. Experimental verification of the cell performance, ultimately with beam, is important and detailed in section 5.b.
- **Superconducting Magnets:** A new systematic analytical approach has allowed specification of target parameters for all the magnets and concepts exist. Experimental verification is needed to establish that the HTS solenoids and Nb₃Sn dipoles can achieve performance that pushes beyond already achieved values. The feasibility of HTS dipoles has to be established for the second project stage. IMCC seeks to leverage development in magnet technology to improve performance. IMCC plans to use high field solenoids throughout the muon production system. HTS, which is coming online commercially, will be fully exploited. Solenoids with fields up to 25 % higher than the current state of the art will need a strong R&D programme to realise. In other areas solenoids having significant forces, stored energies and stresses will need R&D to deliver. Further work is foreseen for dipoles, quadrupoles and combined function magnets in the high energy complex. Development of final focus magnets and collider ring dipoles will be particularly important to yield the ultimate luminosity.
- **Fast booster magnets and power converter:** Concepts for the fast booster magnets and the power converters exist that can reach the required performance. Further optimisation and experimental demonstration is required.
- **RF systems:** Concepts for the cavities along the complex are required. In particular an optimisation of the beamloading and the couplers is required to minimise the overall cost and power consumption while maintaining good beam quality. Power losses induced by muon decay products heating the superconducting RCS cavities should be minimised, as they could in the worst case require up to almost 30 MW of electric power to cool.
- **Schedule, Cost and Power:** The comprehensive R&D program will minimize risks to the project's schedule, cost and power consumption. The key R&D that is most critical for the schedule is given in section 5.b. The R&D programme covers the important cost and power drivers and will inform future cost estimates and power consumption assessments.

Sufficient resources in terms of personnel and material are key to mitigate the **risk for the schedule**. A coherent strategy to secure the resources is essential for timely implementation of the R&D programme and requires a centralised process. An important part of the resources could be provided through the CERN MTP and be complemented with resources from other institutions with commitments taken in a coherent agreement, for example through the LDG or a similar organisation.

6 Dependencies

6.a Whether a specific host site is foreseen, or whether options are available

IMCC is developing a site independent design, which could be realised at any location. It is also exploring two main specific implementations at this moment, one at CERN and one at FNAL. The proposed layouts are shown in Figure 6.a. At these sites the muon collider can potentially benefit from existing infrastructure, e.g. at CERN from the SPS and LHC tunnels. For CERN this would impact the energy choices, currently 3.2 TeV for the first and 7.6 TeV for the second stage. The site specific studies also allow addressing the neutrino flux.

Fig. 6.a: Conceptual layout of the muon collider at CERN (left) and Fermilab (right).

6.b The dependencies on existing or required infrastructure

The muon collider can benefit from existing infrastructure but does not depend on it.

An initial exploration of a muon collider **implementation at CERN** has been carried out. It concludes that

- There is at least one implementation of the collider ring that enables an exquisite neutrino physics programme while also mitigating the neutrino flux from the experimental insertions.
- The proton complex could be implemented on the CERN site, for example on the Meyrin site, using a layout planned for the SPL.
- The muon production target could be installed on the Preveessin site.
- The muon cooling complex could be installed in a cut-and-cover tunnel in the Preveessin site; the klystrons and modulators could then be conveniently placed in a building above the beam tunnel.
- Similarly the initial linacs and recirculating linacs could be installed at Preveessin.
- The beam can then be injected into the SPS tunnel, which can house one (baseline) or two (alternative) RCS rings. The RCS would be a normal design where the magnets are only ramped up in field.
- From the SPS the beam can be injected into the LHC tunnel that would house one RCS to accelerate the beam to 1.6 TeV and a second stage that could accelerate to 3.8 TeV. The first stage would use pulsed normal conducting dipoles, while the second stage would be a hybrid RCS comprising fixed superconducting dipoles and pulsed normal conducting dipoles.
- The collider ring is conveniently located to facilitate injection from the LHC.

- All surface construction can be located on CERN land except for the experimental sites. These could also be moved onto CERN land if necessary.

This scenario would enable collision energy as high as 7.6 TeV with the baseline technologies. It could be envisaged to increase the energy by using higher field HTS fast-ramping magnets in the last RCS in the LHC. Alternatively, a second hybrid RCS could be installed in the SPS and the first RCS in the LHC could be hybrid. A detailed study will enable validation of these implementation concepts.

The initial 10 TeV **Muon Collider Fermilab site-filler** concept has been studied and a very preliminary design has been developed. The PIP-II linac will be used as the initial part of the proton source. Ongoing Fermilab proton intensity upgrade plans involve a new proton linac with energy of 0.8 GeV. To get to higher energies (8-16 GeV) needed for the muon collider proton driver, options for a linac or a linac and RCS are being studied. This is followed by a muon collection and bunching section that leads into the 6D muon cooling channels that can deliver exquisite low emittance beams. The collection and cooling channel will be 1-2 km long. Muon acceleration is achieved in multiple stages. The team is considering a 4-stage hybrid RCS scenario. The RCS is constrained to fit within the Fermilab site, restricting the circumference of the largest tunnel to 16.5 km. The first RCS is chosen to include only NC magnets (up to 1.8 T) and to fit a 6280 m circumference so that it could potentially use the existing Tevatron tunnel. Its peak energy would be 450 GeV. The second RCS takes the beam energy up to 1.725 TeV and requires a new tunnel with circumference of 10.5 km. RCS3 and RCS4 are housed in the longest tunnel, which will be 16.5 km long. The 5 TeV beams will be injected into a 10 TeV collider ring which is expected to have a circumference of 10.5 km.

6.c The technical effects of project execution on the operations of existing infrastructures at the host site

At CERN, the muon collider would follow after the completion of HL-LHC. It requires the LHC to be dismantled. However, it is likely possible to maintain the current SPS or to replace its functionality with the new RCS. If the current SPS is kept, operation of the ring will be interrupted during installation of the RCS. Both cases will lead to additional power consumption and an additional overall operations budget.

7 Commentary on current project status

7.a A concise description of the current design / R&D / simulation activities leading to the project, and the community pursuing these

The growing **collaboration** is based on a Memorandum of Cooperation (MoC). The number of signatories has increased to 58 and several more institutes are in the process of joining the collaboration. IMCC succeeded in receiving funding for an EU cofunded design study, MuCol, which started 1.3.2023. The US Particle Physics Project Prioritization Panel recommended in December 2023 to consider hosting a muon collider in the US and joining the IMCC. Discussions with US partners including the Department of Energy's bureau of high-energy physics are on-going. The US community already collaborates strongly in developing the R&D plan for the next decade and is in the process of setting up their national organisation. An inaugural US muon collider community meeting took place at Fermilab in August 2024 with close to 300 participants.

The overall IMCC goal is to carry out the R&D together and to develop options to host the collider at CERN or at FNAL and potentially also other sites. On the 2050 timescale, the muon collider is an important option as an alternative to low energy Higgs factories, that can also deliver energy frontier measurements. At this point progress in several areas is limited by resources and additional resources are being sought across the collaboration, in parallel with the above-mentioned processes to include new partners.

IMCC has improved the status of the muon collider design and the relevant technologies since the last ESPPU mostly by using analytic methods and simulations. Work has focused on the following key areas:

- **Physics Potential.** The unique physics potential of the collider has been further explored. Studies have been performed of the collider's exquisite precision in electroweak physics as well as the potential to explore physics beyond the standard model.
- **Environmental impact.** Beyond the unique physics potential, the compact footprint, limited cost and power consumption have been investigated including a first estimate of cost and wall plug power consumption. This will form the basis for optimisation. A scheme to mitigate the impact of neutrino flux mitigation has been developed.
- A **second detector design study**, MAIA, has started in addition to the existing MUSIC detector design at 10 TeV. Both experiments' design is constrained by beam induced background. Shielding reduces the radiation to levels similar to HL-LHC. Full simulation studies with background including beam-beam pair production indicate that the most relevant physics channel can be studied with near-future technology, in many cases thanks to developments for HL-LHC. Further improvement will be possible with more computing power, improved algorithms and better technology.
- **Machine-detector interface and detector.** Electrons and positrons from muon decays in the collider create showers in the region of the interaction points, referred to as beam induced background (BIB). Tungsten masks protect the detector from the BIB, and detector components with high time and space resolution further reduce this impact. Dedicated studies indicate that the radiation in the detector region is roughly similar to HL-LHC, even if not uniformly distributed.
- **Proton complex.** In the baseline, 2 MW of 5 GeV proton beam at 5 Hz is used for muon production. Proton facilities with larger power are under construction. Lattice designs exist for the two main challenging components, the accumulator and combiner ring that compresses the proton pulses to 2 bunches of 2 ns length. Optimisation is ongoing to minimise collective effects, which could also be addressed by slightly increasing the beam energy.
- **Muon production.** Key challenges for the high-power target have been addressed and showed that a graphite target will survive the shock waves of the incoming beam pulses and the temperature gradients resulting from the removal of the deposited heat. The solenoid surrounding the target is feasible and can be shielded. Work now concentrates on the removal of the proton beam and

mitigation of losses downstream of the target area.

- **Muon cooling technology.** The muon cooling system requires close integration of absorbers and RF cavities in a strong magnetic field. The operation of normal conducting RF cavities in a strong magnetic field can limit the gradient that can be achieved with no breakdown. The MAP study showed that gradients 25% in excess of the design target can be achieved by using cavities with beryllium endplates or by filling the cavities with hydrogen. A prime goal for the collaboration is to design and implement a new facility for further tests of RF cavities in high magnetic field. The collaboration has developed an engineering design of a cooling cell to explore the assembly of its components and their integration into one unit.

The final cooling uses highest-field small aperture solenoids. The goal for the next generation HTS magnets is 40 T and we use this value in the current design effort for the final cooling. Studies of the physical limitations of the cooling design indicate that the emittance target can be reached.

A tentative muon cooling system design now reaches the transverse emittance target of $22.5 \mu\text{m}$. This is a marked improvement compared to the performance of $55 \mu\text{m}$ estimated at the last ESPPU. The longitudinal emittance of 7.7 meV s is well below the target of 22.5 meV s and the MAP design of 26.7 meV s ; this excess performance will likely be used to modify the design parameters and ease the requirements for the collider ring energy acceptance.

- **Muon acceleration.** The muon beam acceleration takes place in a sequence of linacs, recirculating linacs and RCS. Due to resource constraint the focus has been on the RCS that accelerate from ($E_{init} > 60 \text{ GeV}$) to full beam energy. In each RCS the magnet field is ramped up in proportion to the energy gain of the beam. Some synchrotrons are based on a hybrid design where the fast-ramping magnets are interleaved with static superconducting ones. Initial optics designs exist for the site independent RCSs and have been used to derive the component specifications. Conceptual designs for the fast-ramping magnets and associated power converters have been developed and reach the required ramp rates of up to 3.3 kT/s . The energy lost in the magnets is minimised to maintain a satisfactory wall-plug power requirement. An optimal, synchronised ramp shape has been developed for the RF and the magnet field.

An alternative use of fixed field accelerators (FFAs) is also considered.

- **Collider ring.** A solution for 3 TeV collider ring lattice was developed previously and successfully addresses the challenges using Nb₃Sn magnets. The collaboration has now developed a 10 TeV collider ring lattice design that reaches the small beta-function at the collision point using HTS magnets in the interaction region; the energy acceptance must be further optimised.

Studies have determined the required thickness of the shielding to protect the magnets from the high-energy electrons and positrons from muon decay. Two conceptual magnet designs with the corresponding aperture and field are being developed.

- **Collective effects.** A very high muon bunch charge is required to achieve the luminosity goal and can potentially lead to significant collective effects. Initial studies have been performed for the RCSs and collider ring. They showed that impedance and beam-beam effects can be mitigated with careful beamscreen design and feedback. For the muon cooling section, the implementation of muon cooling physics into a CERN tracking code is ongoing and will allow the combination of single particle effects in matter with collective effects. Further efforts to implement all collective effects and develop a start-to-end model of the machine are planned. The impact of imperfections and their mitigation on the beam need to be studied.

- A **start-to-end study** of the beams along the whole complex remains to be done to make robust predictions of, and optimise for, performance, low risk, cost and power consumption. A first preliminary estimate of the total **transmission of muons** predicts 1.5×10^{12} at the collision point, which is 20% below the target. Further studies will address this aiming to improve the sub-system transmission and to increase the initial number of muons with a higher power target.

- **Superconducting magnet technology**, in particular HTS, is a key enabler of the muon collider

and has an important impact on the timeline. Growing use of HTS in society can potentially have an important impact on the cost. For all superconducting magnets studies have been performed taking stored energy, current limits and stress in the coils into account to determine the field levels that can realistically be obtained as a function of the superconductor used, the magnet aperture and cost. These limits have been integrated into the lattice designs. Several conceptual designs of magnets exist. An experimental programme has successfully been started several years ago and its continuation is now essential.

As mentioned above **the demonstrator design at CERN** is progressing and detailed studies of an implementation on CERN site - e.g. in the TT7 tunnel, or CTF3 building - are ongoing.

7.b A statement of any major in-kind deliverables already negotiated

The muon collider is still in the R&D phase and IMCC is developing the muon collider concept and technologies to a maturity level that enables a decision to be made on the implementation of a collider. The focus is thus on the funding of the R&D programme.

The partner institutions support the R&D programme with resources and in addition the European Union is co-funding a design study, MuCol, that has been instrumental in the timely start of the programme. Support has also been provided by the Snowmass process in the US and additional contributions from US partners have started. In particular FNAL plans a site study for the demonstrator and SLAC is building an RF test stand for 1.3 and 3 GHz frequencies. The integrated resources are shown in figure 7.a.

An initial ramp-up of the resources in Europe is instrumental to implement the technology R&D phase and maintain the muon collider as an option by around 2050. Following the ESPPU conclusions and considering global developments, the sharing of the efforts between the regions can be defined for the demonstration phase.

Fig. 7.a: IMCC-specific resources in FTE-years, integrated from 2023–2027 (secured in blue, potential in red).

7.c Any other key technical information points in addition to those captured above, including references to additional public documents addressing the points above.

Further, detailed information can be found in the supplementary report submitted to the European Strategy for Particle Physics [2] (also available at: <https://edms.cern.ch/document/3284682/1>).

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Answers of the International Muon Collaboration to the Questionnaire of the ESG Working Group 2a

IMCC Answers to the ESPPU WG2a

International Muon Collider Collaboration

1 Introduction

In this document we address the questions posed by working group 2a of the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU). We give a short introduction to the muon collider. Then we address the muon collider specific questions and in the following sections the generic questions. The answers are based on the submission to the European Strategy [1], which gives a concise summary, the addendum to the submission [2], which answers questions posed to the submitted projects and the supplementary document [3], which includes a detailed description of the muon collider design, progress and R&D plans.

2 Muon Collider Overview

The muon collider is a unique, compact, high-energy electroweak collider concept that will produce, cool, accelerate and collide two single-bunch muon beams of opposite charge. It is a paradigm-shifting tool for particle physics representing the first collider to combine the high-energy reach of a hadron collider and the high precision of a lepton collider, yielding a physics potential significantly greater than the sum of its individual parts.

The muon collider potential motivates a growing community, with substantial international interest and enthusiasm, with many calling for the scientific community to aim high and "*shoot for the muon*". The innovative nature of the muon collider in accelerator, detector and magnet technologies has attracted a vibrant community of early career researchers across all regions, many of whom are key designers of systems throughout the accelerator complex. This is an important asset for the muon collider and for the fields of accelerator and particle physics in general. Further detailing of the design and improvement of enabling technologies are essential to make the muon collider a reality. However, it is important to emphasise that no technological showstoppers have been identified in any studies of the muon collider.

The baseline muon collider design is a 10 TeV centre-of-mass collider providing an integrated luminosity of 10 ab^{-1} [4].

Fig. 1: Conceptual layout of the muon collider.

The design of the muon collider is based on a concept, which was developed by the U.S. Muon Accelerator Programme (MAP) until 2017 [5]. The design is now being progressed by the International Muon Collider Collaboration (IMCC) [3, 6]. A schematic layout of the collider is shown in Figure 1 and contains the following key areas:

1. The **proton driver** (blue box in the diagram) produces a short, high-intensity proton pulse.
2. This pulse hits the **target** (indigo) and produces pions. The decay channel guides the pions and forms a beam with the resulting muons via a buncher and phase rotator system.
3. Several **cooling** stages (purple) reduce the longitudinal and transverse emittance of the beam using a sequence of absorbers and RF cavities in a high magnetic field.

4. A system of a linac and two recirculating linacs **accelerate** (light red) the beams to 63 GeV followed by a sequence of high-energy accelerator rings which reach 1.5 TeV or 5 TeV.
5. Finally the beams are injected at full energy into the **collider** ring (red). Here, they will circulate and collide within the detectors until they decay.

Table 1 shows the key parameters for a site independent implementation of a 3 TeV and a 10 TeV centre-of-mass energy stage. These are target parameters conceived to explore the limits of each technology and design. If they can be fully met, the integrated luminosity goal could be reached within five years (or 2.5 years, with two detectors) of full luminosity operation. This provides margin for further design and technology studies and a realistic ramp-up of the luminosity.

An implementation at CERN is under consideration and could reuse the existing SPS and LHC tunnels to accelerate the muon beam. This design could reach a centre-of-mass collision energy of up to 7.6 TeV and a practical initial energy stage could reach up to 3.2 TeV, depending on the layout. The significant reduction of civil engineering and associated environmental impact may justify the slight reduction in physics scope. The initial stage could be implemented by around 2050 [3].

Example parameters for a CERN implementation are shown assuming that a single collider ring tunnel is constructed and used for both energy stages, which is consistent with the use of Nb₃Sn magnets at full energy. If two independent collider rings at CERN are used with Nb₃Sn dipoles for the 3.2 TeV and high-temperature superconductors (HTS) for the 7.6 TeV stage, the luminosities would increase to $2 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $10.1 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively. Use of fast-ramping HTS magnets in the muon acceleration might enable increase of the final energy stage to close to 10 TeV; R&D is required to verify that such an option is practical.

Table 1: Tentative target parameters for a muon collider at different energies. The site independent scenario uses Nb₃Sn technology in the collider ring that is consistent with a project implementation by 2050. The CERN scenario reuses the SPS and LHC tunnels and assumes a 11 km collider tunnel, while the initial studies assumed 10 km. The estimated luminosity refers to the value that can be reached if all target specifications can be reached, including beam-beam effects.

Parameter	Symbol	unit	Site independent		CERN	
			Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 1	Stage 2
Centre-of-mass energy	E_{cm}	TeV	3	10	3.2	7.6
Target integrated luminosity	$\int \mathcal{L}_{\text{target}}$	ab ⁻¹	1	10	1	10
Estimated luminosity	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{estimated}}$	$10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$	1.8	17.5	0.9	7.9
Collider circumference	C_{coll}	km	4.5	11.4	11	11
Collider arc peak field	B_{arc}	T	11	14	4.8	11
Collider dipole technology			Nb ₃ Sn	HTS	NbTi	Nb ₃ Sn or HTS

3 Answers to the Specific Questions

3.1 General

Are there start-to-end performance simulations that allow the assessment of the robustness of key parameters such as luminosity, cost, and energy consumption, and enable performance optimization and so on?

To optimise the use of the limited resources, the simulation studies and code development focused on the most critical areas of the collider. The beam parameters were defined at the interfaces between areas to allow their individual design and optimisation in collaboration with the required technology development. Key examples of the studies are the design and simulation of the proton accumulation and combination complex, the target, the 6D and final cooling, the RCS chain, the collider ring and the machine-detector interface. The CERN-based RFTrack code has been modified to include the muon-matter interaction to simulate the muon cooling and the beam-beam simulation code GUINEA-PIG has been modified to simulate muon beam collisions and background generation. The completion of a fully integrated study of the collider is an important focus of the proposed R&D but requires sufficient resources.

Important studies were performed to identify realistic performance specifications for novel components and optimise the lattice designs and the beam performance accordingly. Some key examples are:

- The magnet team developed a model that allows to predict the achievable field as a function of technology, aperture, operating temperature and cost. This model informed the lattice designs. For the actual costing detailed designs were used.
- The radial build of the collider ring magnets is the result of the work of a team of experts for lattice design, collective effects, beam-matter interactions, cryogenics, vacuum and magnets.
- Similarly, the target design includes beam-matter interactions, cryogenics and magnet design.
- Beam dynamics and vacuum experts studied the heat deposition in the final cooling absorbers and determined the hydrogen vapor density acceptable for the windows.
- In the RCSs, the fast-ramping magnet-power converter systems and the RF systems need to be synchronised to meet the beam dynamics requirements. Models of the power consumption and cost of the systems were derived and implemented into a code that was used to optimise the system.

A bottom-up cost model of the collider exists, which covers the key cost drivers, more detail can be found in section 6. Also the power consumption has been estimated bottom-up considering the key drivers, see section 9.2. Following completion of the start-to-end simulation, an integrated optimisation will be performed that should yield improvement in cost, power and performance of the system and reduce the risk.

3.2 R&D Plan

- What are the resources expected from CERN and from other partners to cover the proposed R&D plan? For example, the developments of the high field HTS magnet and the RF systems need large scale funding.
- An independent review of scope, schedule, and cost for the R&D program over the coming 10 years will be needed to justify it. Is such a review planned?
- Is the organization or group defined that leads the R&D activities and coordinates the budget and human resources?

The IMCC R&D programme is presented in the various input documents to the ESPP update in May 2025: in particular chapters 7-13 of the ESPP input backup document [3]. Chapter 7.4

of this reference provides an overview of the 10 year programme (objectives and deliverables), chapter 7.3 presents the resource breakdown, included also here in table 2. A concise summary can be found in chapter 5 of [2].

Year	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
Accelerator Design and Technologies										
Material	1.6	3.2	4.8	6.4	9.6	10.8	12.0	12.0	12.0	12.0
FTE	47.1	60.6	75.0	85.0	100.0	120.0	150.0	174.6	177.2	185.1
Demonstrator										
Material	0.6	2.2	3.9	5.4	7.8	15.1	25.9	32.4	31.8	12.6
FTE	9.5	11.0	12.5	29.2	29.7	30.5	25.5	27.7	26.7	25.5
Detector										
Material	0.5	1.1	1.6	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.6	3.1	3.1
FTE	23.4	46.5	70.0	93.0	93.0	93.0	93.0	116.4	139.5	139.5
Magnets										
Material	3.0	4.9	10.1	10.0	11.0	13.4	11.7	7.2	6.6	4.7
FTE	23.3	28.4	36.4	40.9	44.3	47.1	46.2	37.7	36.1	29.4
TOTALS										
Material	5.7	11.4	20.3	23.9	30.6	41.4	51.7	54.2	53.5	32.4
FTE	103.3	146.5	194.0	248.1	267.0	290.6	314.8	356.3	379.4	379.6

Table 2: Summary of R&D resources, divided by area, over a ten year period. Personnel is given as average Full Time Equivalent (FTE), where students count as 50% FTE. Material is given in millions of CHF (MCHF). The total is the sum of the four areas.

The R&D programme is described very briefly in the following, please see the above-mentioned references for a detailed description: The programme demonstrates muon cooling technology through component development, integrated tests, and a dedicated demonstrator facility. It includes construction and testing of superconducting magnets, particularly HTS solenoids, with strong links to societal applications and industrial developments, and model dipoles for the collider ring. A complete start-to-end collider model with refined lattice design, beam physics simulations, and availability studies will guide component choices and luminosity predictions. Target robustness will be verified experimentally. Conceptual and experimental work on superconducting and normal-conducting RF cavities, including tests in high magnetic fields, will optimise design, supported by high-power, high-efficiency klystron development. Demonstration of fast-ramping magnets and power converters for RCS is foreseen. Site and environmental studies will ensure minimal impact, while global optimisation of cost, power, and risk will guide the facility design.

As can be seen from table 2, to deliver the proposed R&D programme in time a very significant ramp-up of resources is required. The ESPPU recommendation will be instrumental for further funding of the muon collider efforts across Europe. Currently 61 institutions are full members of the collaboration, and thus at this early stage express the willingness to contribute. The EU co-funds a design study, MuCol, which has 30 partners, several of which are not yet full collaboration members. At present, several DOE national laboratories have allocated LDRD funds to support muon collider work, supplemented by contributions from GARD. Universities in the United States use fractions of base Energy Frontier funding and dedicated grants from private foundations. Funding in the U.S. is ramping up and budget on the scale of significant hardware investment is expected around 2030, when many ongoing large U.S. projects are completed. Many U.S. institutions are already members of the IMCC, and once the addendum for the muon collider to the CERN-DOE agreement is finalized, national laboratories in the U.S. will also officially join international efforts.

To maintain the momentum that IMCC has built up, the timely ramp-up of resources for the R&D programme is instrumental. In the first five years, Europe institutions should carry a large part of the effort and provide through CERN an important part of the human resources and the

lion share of the material budget. In 2028, results of the ESPPU and the sub-subsequent review panel recommended by P5 will be available. A decision on the location of the demonstrator could be made together with a review of the sharing of efforts for the second half of the proposed R&D phase.

Strong synergy with societal applications exists, a prime example are the HTS solenoids for the target and fusion reactors. Therefore all regions might want to profit from this opportunity.

The IMCC R&D programme is the core of the next phase of the muon collider project and has been presented and reviewed in several places:

- The LDG review in the February 2025 [7]. The comments of the review committee can be found in the closeout of the same meeting.
- The comments and feedback from this initial review were incorporated in the R&D programme presented in the various input documents to the ESPP update in May 2025 as described above [2, 3].
- To address the overall completeness and soundness of the programme the IMCC International Advisory Committee (IAC)¹ reviewed the R&D programme in June-July 2025 and concluded: "During its current IMCC review, the IAC was highly impressed by the significant progress and the marked improvement in the robustness and quality of the studies. The muon collider presents an extraordinary technical opportunity, and encouragingly, all major technical challenges are being actively tackled. In particular, launching and supporting a cooling demonstrator and test stands as soon as possible will be crucial to sustaining this strong momentum." The detailed report is being finalised. The presentations to the IAC (17.6 and 20.6.2025) can be found at [8].
- The LDG will update the European Accelerator R&D Roadmap in 2026, which will help to further refine the programme and to provide resources. The immediate next step is an extended LDG meeting and review planned for February 2026. Within IMCC, an R&D Task Force is in the process of identifying who can contribute to the R&D programme implementation, how the work could be distributed and how funding can be secured. This task force, with the IMCC management, will also address the milestones, decision points, and risk-analysis for the R&D programme.

The muon collider R&D is performed in the frame of the International Muon Collider Collaboration, which is hosted at CERN. Its organisation is based on a Memorandum of Cooperation (MoC). An International Collaboration Board (ICB) represents the member institutions and a Steering Board oversees the work. An International Advisory Committee regularly reviews the progress of the work and the plans. IMCC reports to the LDG and via MuCol also to the European Union. The organisation will be updated to accommodate the increasing U.S. participation. An addendum to the CERN-DoE agreement is being prepared for the muon collider, the latest version has been sent by DoE to CERN.

The executive part of the study contains workpackages for physics, detector and the different parts and technologies of the machine. The workpackage leaders meet weekly in the Coordination Committee.

¹The IAC consists of several permanent members: Ursula Bassler (chair), Mauro Mezzetto, Hongwei Zhao, Akira Yamamoto, Maurizio Vretenar, Stewart Boogert, Sarah, Demers, Giorgio Apollinari and experts for this review: Pierre Vedrine, Stephen Gourlay, Lyn Evans, Alessandro Gallo, Barbara Dalena, Pantaleo Raimondi.

3.3 Demonstrator

- Many critical R&D items, such as muon cooling, target for 2 MW, high field magnet etc., need to be proven feasible. Are the scopes of demonstrator defined? What do you want to show or prove by the demonstrator programs?
- In particular, could you describe what the demonstrator will be able to demonstrate in terms of reduction of transverse and longitudinal emittance, which is necessary to achieve the beam brightness required for collider luminosity (a reduction of several orders of magnitude compared to the initial muon source)?
- Could you provide a breakdown of costs (personnel and materials) for the demonstrator?

The R&D programme discussed above includes hardware development of muon cooling, target for 2 MW, high-field magnets etc. The Demonstration of Muon Cooling will demonstrate the engineering feasibility and beam performance of the 6D muon cooling system, which provides the majority of the required emittance reduction.

Delivery of the Demonstration of Muon Cooling will require a programme of R&D to understand and mitigate risks surrounding construction of the cooling lattice. The principle issues are:

1. The cooling cell has RF cavities and solenoids in close proximity. Solenoid fields are known to induce RF breakdown which must be understood in detail. MAP demonstrated RF performance significantly beyond that required for the IMCC cooling system, but for a single cavity operating in a single frequency configuration.
2. Very compact HTS solenoids must be developed under high forces with limited space for insulation.
3. Remote handling of beam-pipe connections, necessitated by tight geometrical constraints, has been highlighted as the most critical challenge by design reviews.
4. The integrated facility must be operable in a routine manner and deliver satisfactory performance.

In order to deliver this, a staged R&D programme is envisaged, with each stage demonstrating the technology more fully:

1. Several RF test stands will be constructed to understand the limits to RF gradient that can be achieved in the presence of high-field solenoids. SLAC has begun a programme of tests for RF cavity operation in magnetic fields initially focused at high frequency characteristic of existing RF sources.
2. A one-cell module will be implemented in order to test the operation of RF cavities in an operational magnetic environment. INFN and UMIL are developing a split-coil solenoid system within the RFMFTF facility to test RF operation in magnetic fields, supported by national and institutional funding. For remote connections, customized pillow seals form the baseline solution, with radial sealing, integrated cryostat designs, and Shape-Memory Alloys considered as alternatives. Each option balances feasibility, reliability, and development risk.
3. A multi-cell module will be implemented to demonstrate integration of absorber, RF and magnets. Suitable RF power sources and cavities are under study at Univ. Lancaster, INFN and UMIL, CEA Saclay and CERN.
4. The multi-cell module will be operated with beam in order to demonstrate commissioning and operation of the cooling equipment with beam. CERN, Imperial College and STFC are studying pion transport, cooling channel beam physics design and implementation at CERN, with implementation plans prepared for different siting options having different advantages in terms of cost and impact. Fermilab is studying possible implementations in the U.S..
5. A cooling line comprising several cooling modules will be implemented to demonstrate

beam physics performance. This will be part of the Project Preparation Phase beyond the detailed R&D programme.

Beam physics performance of the 6D cooling system is determined by the final emittance and fraction of muons transmitted. In the 6D cooling system, each stage reduces beam emittance until it approaches an equilibrium, and then the beam is transferred to the next cooling stage. In this way the emittance of the produced muons is determined by the equilibrium emittance of the final stage of the 6D cooling channel and uncertainty in performance of intermediate stages do not contribute to uncertainty in the delivered beam emittance. Uncertainty on equilibrium emittance is small.

Transmission loss accumulates from one cooling stage to the next. Verification of the transmission loss is therefore important. The IMCC will constrain uncertainty in transmission loss and corresponding luminosity uncertainty to a satisfactory level.

The estimated material and effort required to prepare a one cell module for power testing and to implement a the initial demonstrator facility at the TT7 beamline at CERN is listed in Table 3 and a potential timeline is shown in Figure 3.

Year	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
One-Cell Module										
Staff	4	4.5	7	7	5.5	4.5	0	0	0	0
Post doc	5	6	5	5	5	4	0	0	0	0
Student	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material	0.6	2.25	3.9	4.8	4.35	0.7	0	0	0	0
Multi-Cell Module										
Staff	0	0	0	5.5	5.5	6	7	7	7.5	7
Post doc	0	0	0	3	4	4	5	6	6	6
Student	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material	0	0	0	0.3	1.5	7.2	11.2	12.7	9.9	6.3
TT7										
Staff	0	0	0	4.7	4.7	7	8.5	8.7	7.2	6.5
Post doc	0	0	0	4	5	5	5	6	6	6
Student	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material	0	0	0	0.3	2.0	7.2	14.7	19.7	21.9	6.3
TOTALS										
Material	0.6	2.2	3.9	5.4	7.8	15.1	25.9	32.4	31.8	12.6
Personnel	9.5	11.0	12.5	29.2	29.7	30.5	25.5	27.7	26.7	25.5

Table 3: Estimated resource requirement for the implementation of the Initial Muon Cooling Demonstrator in TT7. The material is given in MCHF, personnel in FTEy. The resource requirement does not include the resource for individual RF Test Stands.

3.4 Performance / Site preparation

- What is the maximum beam energy of the muon collider at CERN that would ensure neutrino radiation constraints do not restrict access to areas outside the muon collider complex (e.g., the CERN site)?

The current siting strategy for the muon collider is based on limiting the neutrino flux from the arcs to a negligible level and acquiring some land where the narrow cone of the neutrino flux in direction of the experimental straights exits the surface. The goal was to establish that at least one site exists that is suitable for 7.6 TeV. The full optimisation has not yet been completed. However, one candidate collider ring site and orientation appears to be a solution and is described in this document in section 10. For this solution, the highest flux in the fenced area corresponds to

the situation in an airplane. The optimisation of the orientation around this initial point is ongoing considering the details of the surface.

The currently considered tentative site and orientation combines a number of advantages. One site is on an uninhabited, descending mountain slope and the neutrinos will not re-entre the Earth at larger distance. One can place a neutrino experiment at this location. The other site is located in the sea at a large distance which reduces the flux strongly. The collider is also well connected to the LHC tunnel and the CERN site. Further potential sites and collider orientations will be sought to reduce the risk that suitable permits and consents cannot be found at the currently proposed site.

4 Scope

- Provide Work Breakdown Structure (expected granularity down to at least 100 MCHF or better) with associated scope definition.

The focus of the study is on the proposed R&D programme. The workpackages and their cost is shown in Table 2 and discussed in section 3.2 above. Here we focus on the cost estimate for the collider, which informs the design and the R&D programme.

The approach to the cost estimate of the Muon Collider project and the analysis of the most significant sources of cost uncertainty is directly linked to the technical maturity of the project itself. The Muon Collider design is in a CDR stage, where its architecture is developed to a certain level of detail and the main beam parameters are known with some accuracy, but still several options exist that may steer the project into different directions, with considerable impact on the final cost.

The goal of the whole exercise is to develop the knowledge for a Rough Order of Magnitude (ROM) estimate that is provided in the form of a cost range for the different versions of the machine, with also the ambition of providing guidelines for the best trade-off when a decision between competing technical choices comes into play.

Hence, the cost estimate that is presented here is not meant for a cost comparison with more mature projects, which are already in their approval phase.

The different scenarios were already described in Chapter 2 and summarized in Table 1. The site-independent case with collision energy of 10 TeV was considered for comparison. The adopted scheme shows that a staged approach is possible, following the progressive development of the high field superconducting magnet technology.

The Muon Collider WBS structure is shown in Table 4 with an example of a record. It is based on a four level architecture, with increasing levels of detail, from Domain level down to Equipment level. Due to the early stage of the project not all Domains present the same granularity in the costing, however the present cost structure provides sufficient flexibility to include the gradual refinement of the cost data for all Domains. A Class of uncertainty has been associated to each line of the WBS, directly providing the associated cost uncertainty for a specific Equipment or Technical System.

Table 4: The WBS architecture for the Muon Collider facility, with the RCS1 record shown as an example.

Domain	WBS			Class of Uncertainty	Description
	Sub-domain	Tech. System	Equipment		
4	4.4	4.4.1			Muon Acceleration Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons RCS1
			4.4.1.1	3	RCS1 RF System
			4.4.1.2	4	RCS1 NC Magnets
			4.4.1.3	4	RCS1 Power Converters

Class of uncertainties have been derived with reference to the practice guideline 18R-97 developed by the Association for the Advancement of Cost Engineering (AACE), by assuming the mid-point of the cost range provided by the AACE table for the low and high part of the cost range respectively. The cost uncertainties as they were associated to each uncertainty Class are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Cost uncertainty associated to the different uncertainty classes that were considered in the exercise.

Class	Negative Uncertainty [%]	Positive Uncertainty [%]
3	-15	+20
4	-22.5	+35
5	-35	+65

5 Schedule

- Provide overall schedule based on WBS including required R&D milestones and needed test facilities (if any).

The muon collider concept requires significant R&D to achieve the maturity level needed for implementation. The timeline is largely driven by the progress of this R&D programme and the available funding. We focus on the technical limitations, strategic and budgetary considerations will be integrated as they become available from the ESPPU and the sub-subsequent medium-term review panel proposed by P5.

In Europe, hosting the collider is being considered either following a Higgs factory or as the next flagship project after the HL-LHC. In the United States, there is strong interest in hosting the collider to reassert leadership at the high-energy frontier.

To guide the definition of the R&D programme, an ambitious technically limited timeline has been explored together by European and U.S. experts; the phases are shown in Table 6. This scenario prioritizes reuse of existing CERN infrastructure to minimize civil engineering costs and limits the collider’s center-of-mass energy of the first stage to approximately 3 TeV, consistent with realistic expectations for the development of high-field HTS dipole magnets.

The **Initial Phase** is ongoing and its efforts need to be continued and increased throughout the overall programme. The **Demonstration Phase** focuses on further advancing the design and the technologies to a level that allows the feasibility of a muon collider to be demonstrated with confidence. A specific decision is required to launch this phase (at time T_0 in Table 6) once the siting and funding of the demonstrator have been established. This could be 2028 or later, considering the results of the ESPPU, the funding situation in the U.S. and the technical progress. The Demonstration Phase requires a minimum of seven years to produce a technical design of the demonstrator and to construct the initial facility, which consists of a muon beam production section and an ionisation cooling module. During this phase also the placement of the collider would be defined. Once the demonstration is successful (at T_1) the **Project Preparation Phase** can start, which requires an increased investment to allow the construction of the final demonstrator by adding a sequence of modules, to complete the R&D on the main technologies and start their industrialisation, to evaluate the environmental impact of the project implementation and to go through the authorisation process. Ground breaking can follow (at T_2) and launch the **Construction Phase**, for which we assume 9 years including commissioning.

With a firm commitment to implementing a muon collider in Europe as soon as possible after the HL-LHC, operation could start around 2050, see Figure 2 for the technically limited schedule. The energy and luminosity reach of this machine are dependent on the progress of the more generic magnet R&D program. In 2050, we do not anticipate the availability of HTS dipoles for use in the collider ring. The well-established NbTi technology could allow a reach of 3 TeV. To target higher energies, Nb₃Sn dipoles are considered. Following the FCC-hh magnet timeline, we expect this technology to be available on the 2050 timescale, and the much smaller collider ring size should allow a comparatively shorter production time. Unlike HTS dipoles, HTS solenoids are expected to have reached sufficient maturity to be utilized in the muon cooling channel. The timeline for the Demonstrator is shown in Figure 3 and for the magnet development in Figure 4; they are consistent with the overall timeline.

U.S. siting follows similar schedule constraints. The technically limited timeline established in the U.S. as part of the Snowmass process closely resembles the European timeline [9]. Small differences (few years over this approximately 25-year schedule) arise due primarily to assumptions around ramp-up time in each region. Siting in the U.S. requires consideration of the timelines of ongoing U.S. based projects, particularly the DUNE schedule. DUNE Phase 1 construction will conclude in 2031, and its Phase 2, if approved, will go through a construction phase while Phase 1 operates, during the 2030s. These constraints align well with the prospect of muon collider start of construction in mid 2040s.

A U.S.-hosted muon collider would have strong synergies with an FCC program at CERN. Concurrent with a Higgs Factory, it could explore higher energy electroweak phenomena [10], while also providing precision PDF measurements that could constrain uncertainties on FCC-hh collisions, allowing it to take full advantage of its unparalleled reach for strong phenomena [11].

Meanwhile, there are also options for muon collider siting at CERN after the 2050s. Higgs factories like LEP3 or a low-energy LCF could serve as bridge projects, starting quickly after the HL-LHC shut-down. A muon collider designed to begin operations in the mid-2060s could take advantage of the improvements in magnet technology, and target higher energies with a more compact footprint. Looking further into the future, a U.S.-based muon collider could serve as a proving ground for an even higher energy muon collider sited at CERN at timescales similar to FCC-hh.

Unlocking the ability to collide muons provides a rich future for high energy physics, extending beyond the 10 TeV scale. All variants of this path start with today’s R&D. The first phase (up to and including the Demonstrator Phase in Table 6) focuses on advancing the design and required technologies to a level that allows the feasibility of a muon collider to be demonstrated with confidence. Expected key deliverables of this phase are listed in [2] and more detail is given in [3]. The estimated resource requirements for this phase are approximately 320 million CHF in materials and 2700 full-time equivalent years (FTEy) in personnel, including 20 million CHF and 900 FTEy allocated to detector development, see Table 2 and section 3.2. This phase is expected to last a minimum of 10 years.

Investments since the last ESPPU have placed Europe as a leader in the muon collider effort. Nonetheless, current R&D progress is severely limited by available resources, despite the fact that technically-limited timelines in Europe and the U.S. align well with facility availability. A continued ramp-up of the global muon collider effort is necessary to demonstrate muon collider technology and complete a start-to-end design of a machine.

IMCC plans to review the Roadmap in 2028, following the results of the upcoming ESPPU and the subsequent mid-term review panel recommended by the P5 report. At that point, a decision can be made on the location of the demonstrator facility and it could be approved.

Fig. 2: Technically limited timeline for the initial muon collider stage, assuming a firm commitment to implement the project as soon as possible after the High-Luminosity LHC. The timeline of the project phases beyond the planned 10 years of R&D are affected by the siting choice and detailed planning by the host laboratory. The proposed R&D plan is marked in dark blue.

Phase and activities	Years
Construction of RF test stands	2025 – 2028
Production of test cavities	2026 – 2039
Operation of test stands	2027 – 2040
Demonstration Phase	$T_0 - (T_0 + 7)$
Demonstrator technical design	
Construction of initial demonstrator	
Construction of muon cooling module (5 cells)	
Definition of the placement scenario for the collider	
Project Preparation Phase	$T_1 - (T_1 + 5)$
Final demonstrator	
Implementation studies with the Host states	
Environmental evaluation & project authorisation processes	
Main technologies R&D completion	
Industrialisation of key components	
Engineering Design completion	
Construction Phase (from ground breaking)	$T_2 - (T_2 + 9)$
Civil engineering	
Techn. installation	
Component construction	
Accelerator installation	
HW commissioning	
Beam commissioning	
Physics operation start	$T_2 + 10$

Table 6: The different phases of the timeline.

Fig. 3: Technically limited timeline for the Muon Cooling Demonstrator programme, including the prerequisite RF R&D.

6 Cost

Provide:

- Cost estimate breakdown (2024 prices) according to the WBS (including uncertainty—AACE categorization or similar).
- Description of the methodology for the assessment of the cost uncertainty.

The cost estimate was developed by analyzing the key cost drivers across civil engineering, technical infrastructure, the cryogenic and magnet systems, power converters, and the RF system, including RF power generation. Workpackage leaders in charge of different technological areas corresponding to those cost drivers were asked to provide their estimates, together with the level of maturity for the specific technology. We tried to use a bottom-up approach wherever possible and cost scaling from known projects in other cases. A methodology, common to mature projects like

Fig. 4: Technically limited timeline for the Muon Magnet programme.

CLIC, FCC and LCF, was used for Civil engineering costing, RCS RF systems, cryogenic system and power converters in general. In Figure 6 the cost range for two scenarios (CERN installation for two distinct energies and Green Field) is presented on a billion CHF scale. Red markers show the position of the most probable value.

Figure 5 shows the relative distribution of cost for the Muon Collider facility at 7.6 TeV with respect to different technologies and Domains.

Fig. 5: Relative cost distribution by technology (left) and by Domain (right) for the 7.6 TeV Muon Collider facility.

The details of the class of uncertainty associated to each cost line are provided in Table 7. More details about the applied method are provided for each cost driver and listed below.

Civil Engineering

A complete estimate of cost was produced for the CERN based installation, by adopting the same methodology and cost database used also for other projects, like CLIC and the FCC. This includes all elements that are displayed in Figure 9, with the exception of the existing tunnels of SPS and LHC, which are used to host the rapid cycling synchrotrons (RCS). For the cost estimate of the green field scenario a cost of 50 kEUR/m was used for RCS and collider tunnels. Class IV uncertainty was adopted for the Civil Engineering estimate.

Table 7: WBS table with explicit indication of the Class of uncertainty for the considered lines of cost. Domain 6, the Detectors, have not been included in the costing.

Domain	Sub-domain	Tech. System	Equipment	Class of Uncertainty	Description
1	1.1			4	Proton Driver SC Linac
2	2.1 2.2	2.2.1		5 5	Front End Pion production target Pion decay channel Decay channel solenoids
3	3.2 3.4	3.2.1 3.2.2 3.4.2		5 5 5	Muon cooling channel Rectilinear cooling channel Cooling RF system Cooling solenoids Final cooling Final cooling solenoids
4	4.3 4.4	4.3.1 4.4.1 4.4.2 4.4.3 4.4.4	4.4.1.1 4.4.1.2 4.4.1.3 4.4.2.1 4.4.2.2 4.4.2.3 4.4.2.4 4.4.2.5 4.4.3.1 4.4.3.2 4.4.3.3 4.4.3.4 4.4.3.5 4.4.4.1 4.4.4.2 4.4.4.3 4.4.4.4 4.4.4.5	4 3 4 4 3 5 4 4 3 5 4 4 3 5 4 4 3 5 4 4	Muon Acceleration Recirculating Linacs RL RF system Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons RCS1 RCS1 RF System RCS1 NC Magnets RCS1 Power Converters (NC) RCS2 RCS2 RF System RCS2 SC Magnets RCS2 Power Converters (SC) RCS2 NC Magnets RCS2 Power Converters (NC) RCS3 RCS3 RF System RCS3 SC Magnets RCS3 Power Converters (SC) RCS3 NC Magnets RCS3 Power Converters (NC) RCS4 RCS4 RF System RCS4 SC Magnets RCS4 Power Converters (SC) RCS4 NC Magnets RCS4 Power Converters (NC)
5	5.2 5.4			5 5	Collider ring SC Magnets Tungsten shielding
7	7.1 7.2 7.3 7.4			4 5 5 4	Civil Engineering and Technical Infrastructure Surface buildings and tunnels Electrical system Cooling and Ventilation Cryogenics

Fig. 6: The cost range is presented for the scenario of energy staging of the Muon Collider facility as compared to the Green Field realization. The cost for each stage represents the cost for a complete facility. The darkest part of the colour band identifies the most probable range, while the lighter sides of the band materialize the extension of the calculated uncertainty. Red markers show the position of the most probable value.

Technical Infrastructure

The costs for Electrical Distribution, Cooling and Ventilation were derived by scaling figures from the CLIC cost estimate, which followed a consistent methodology used in other large projects (FCC, LCF). Scaling was based on the total power requirements, heat dissipation estimates, and tunnel length. It was also assumed that the existing SPS and LHC tunnels would not need significant upgrades. Class V uncertainty was considered for both systems.

Normal Conducting Magnets and Power Converters

The design of rapid-cycling synchrotrons (RCS) for future accelerator projects requires a reliable estimation of the costs of both normal-conducting magnets and their associated power converters. As no comparable large-scale reference systems currently exist, a bottom-up modelling approach has been developed to provide first-order cost assessments. The methodology is implemented in a dedicated Python suite, **PoMaRCS**, which integrates electromagnetic dimensioning of magnets with cost models for power electronic components. For magnets, the model evaluates conductor and steel masses, active dimensions, and electrical requirements. Costs are derived from unit material values based on historical references and recent procurement data. For power converters, the model considers a modular architecture composed of thousands of series-connected power electronic cells. Each cell is analyzed in terms of semiconductor devices, power stacks, capacitors, charger, and cabinet. Unit costs are taken from a combination of manufacturer quotes, recent purchases, and informed estimates. The resulting models provide total costs for different RCS scenarios, highlighting contributions from magnets and power converters separately. Although focused on hardware costs only, the approach offers a transparent and reproducible basis for comparing design options. Integration aspects such as installation, cabling, cooling, and civil engineering are not included at this stage [12].

Superconducting Magnets

The cost of the magnet system has been computed using an analytical "bottom-up" approach, based on a rather conventional evaluation of material and labor costs. The method for superconducting accelerator magnets is described in detail in [13], together with the parameters used for the evaluation of the cost of the materials that have the largest contribution to the total system cost. We believe that this is the best method, at this stage, to obtain a good projection of cost, superior

to scaling.

The primary cost drivers for the 6D cooling cells are the REBCO superconducting tape and the mechanical components, due to the high stress requirements. A detailed cost evaluation of the magnets and structure for all cooling cells was based on the design work performed on the demonstrator cooling cell (MuCol WP8). Specifically, the amount of structure required in each cooling cell was obtained by scaling the structure of the demonstrator cell by the electromagnetic force acting on the coils in the other cells.

In the evaluation of the cost we have considered the various phases of development, prototyping, industrialization, pre-series, and production. Costs quoted refer to the pre-series and series production, and do not include tooling and infrastructure costs. Like R&D costs, these introduce little variance with respect to the figures quoted.

The cost of the superconductor is the most significant single position. We have used 2025 cost figures for Nb-Ti, which is consistent with the present market dynamics. For Nb₃Sn we have used HL-LHC cost figures reduced by a factor 3, consistently with FCC-hh estimates, though such a cost reduction is not consistent with present market dynamics (2025 costs have actually increased substantially with respect to HL-LHC). For HTS (REBCO) we have used 2024 cost figures reduced by a factor 3, which is well in line with the present trend in the market.

Radiofrequency Systems

The facility's different areas require distinct RF systems, each utilizing unique technologies that demand customized cost estimation approaches. In the **Cooling Channel** the RF system adopts normal conducting copper cavities, of elliptical shape, whose estimate has been done by means of the FCC RF costing tool. A large cost variance must be introduced in this estimate, having considered the untested context of operation of cavities under large solenoidal fields. The RF systems for the **Recirculating Linacs** deploy superconducting cavities operated at 352 MHz and 1056 MHz. For the low frequency system the cost estimate considers copper cavities with Nb coating, four cells per cavity like in LEP, while the high frequency system adopts bulk Nb cavities, with six cells per cavity. Again the estimation was produced by means of the FCC RF costing tool. Cost of power sources is based on offers from industry. The RF system in the **Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons - RCS** adopts SC 1300 MHz, bulk Nb, 9-cell cavities similar to those that were developed for the ILC. The associated cost estimate could be directly scaled from the ILC estimate, which was updated in 2024. Scaling parameters were the peak beam intensity, energy gain and average RF power. Cost estimates were produced in this way for the RF power sources, the cavities and cryostats with RF power couplers and for the cryogenic system.

Additional domains were included in the cost estimate. **The proton driver's** cost estimate could be based on a very detailed report produced by CERN for the SPL and on information from the construction of the ESS Linac. **The target region** was considered with the decay channel solenoids and shielding. An estimate was also produced for the **cryogenic system**, based on static and dynamic loads in SC magnets and RF equipment. In this case the dynamic load induced by beam losses was considered for all SC magnets, but ignored in RF cavities.

The analysis of the cost variance for the different areas of the Muon Collider facility provides useful indications for an effective risk mitigation of cost. In Figure 7 the impact of the proposed R&D activities is shown for the scenario of CERN installation with collision energy at 7.6 TeV.

Fig. 7: The Muon Collider cost variance for the scenario of CERN installation with 7.6 TeV collision energy. On the left side the cost variance as it was evaluated in preparation of the ESPPU submission, on the right side the estimated variance after that the proposed R&D activities had brought the relevant technologies to the expected TRL6 state.

7 Risk

Provide:

- Risk management plan with corresponding mitigation measures and impact (performance, cost, schedule)
- Present evaluation

The proposed R&D program is designed to address the key risks in delivering collision energy and luminosity as well as good experimental conditions and site options within an appropriate cost and time envelope. Risk on the estimated performance of the muon collider and mitigation techniques are described below.

- **Siting:** neutrinos arising from muon decay may create a weak neutron shower near to the surface. Neutrinos may arise from decay of muons in the straight sections near the interaction point or the arcs. An implementation has been identified that mitigates the neutrino flux risk from the interaction point straights. Neutrinos emerge in two non-built-up sites in the Jura mountains and Mediterranean sea, which could provide an ideal location for neutrino physics experiments. In the arcs a system of movers will change the beam angle between -1 mrad and $+1$ mrad in order to make a negligible impact, consistent with the equivalent impact from operation of the LHC. IMCC must demonstrate that the movers can operate remaining within alignment constraints. As the project matures, appropriate permitting and consents must be established for the proposed remote sites.
- **Experimental Conditions:** Muon decay products can impinge on the detectors creating electromagnetic showers that lead to Beam-Induced Background. Tungsten masks protect the detector from the BIB and detector components with high time and space resolution further reduce this impact. Dedicated studies indicate that the radiation in the detector region is roughly similar to HL-LHC, even if not uniformly distributed.
- **Integrated Design:** IMCC has designed key components but a number of other components have not yet been designed. Sufficient accelerator physics resources are required to complete and optimise the lattice design, which can profit from several iterations in difficult cases, and to guide the technology development. The mitigation of collective effects and imperfections along the whole chain is essential to avoid a bottleneck for the bunch charge or emittance growth; an assessment of the component availability and the impact on integrated luminosity is essential. The start-to-end model presents an opportunity; optimisation may yield performance improvements and allows trade-offs between different systems and technologies to be made. It can also uncover risk, which must be managed by further design work.
- **Muon Cooling:** The muon cooling system requires close integration of absorbers, magnets and RF cavities. Large forces between neighbouring magnets must be managed while allow-

ing sufficient space for services to RF cavities. RF cavities must operate at high gradients despite the intense solenoid fields. The IMCC has developed a full engineering design of a typical cooling cell that adequately manages the forces. Previous experiments have demonstrated RF gradients that are 25 % higher than the requirements for the cooling system, but the response to parameters (frequency, magnetic field, etc) has not been fully characterised. Experimental verification of the cell performance, ultimately with beam, is important and discussed in section 3.3.

- **Superconducting Magnets:** A new systematic analytical approach has allowed specification of target parameters for all the magnets and concepts exist. Experimental verification is needed to establish that the HTS solenoids and Nb₃Sn dipoles can achieve performance that pushes beyond already achieved values. The feasibility of HTS dipoles has to be established for the second project stage. IMCC seeks to leverage development in magnet technology to improve performance. IMCC plans to use high field solenoids throughout the muon production system. HTS, which is coming online commercially, will be fully exploited. Solenoids with fields up to 25 % higher than the current state of the art will need a strong R&D programme to realise. In other areas solenoids having significant forces, stored energies and stresses will need R&D to deliver. Further work is foreseen for dipoles, quadrupoles and combined function magnets in the high energy complex. Development of final focus magnets and collider ring dipoles will be particularly important to yield the ultimate luminosity.
- **Fast booster magnets and power converter:** Concepts for the fast booster magnets and the power converters exist that can reach the required performance. Further optimisation and experimental demonstration is required.
- **RF systems:** Concepts for the cavities along the complex are required. In particular an optimisation of the beamloading and the couplers is required to minimise the overall cost and power consumption while maintaining good beam quality. Power losses induced by muon decay products heating the superconducting RCS cavities should be minimised, as they could in the worst case require up to almost 30 MW of electric power to cool.
- **Schedule, Cost and Power:** The comprehensive R&D program will minimize risks to the project's schedule, cost and power consumption. The key R&D that is most critical for the schedule is given in section 8. The R&D programme covers the important cost and power drivers and will inform future cost estimates and power consumption assessments.

8 Technical Readiness Level/R&D Plans/Test Facilities

Provide:

- TRL level of the major subsystems (e.g.: Injectors and transfer lines, Civil engineering, Territorial development, Technical infrastructures, collider/booster, main beam production and transfer lines, drive beam production and transfer lines, Technical Infrastructure, Experiments, ...).
- Indicate the components with the lowest TRL and their TRL.
- Required R&D to establish technical performance of the subsystems and corresponding timeline
- Is it funded (material, supplies and manpower)? and at which level as compared to expectations?
- Risk mitigation plans in case R&D is not successful and their impact (performance, cost, schedule)
- Is a new / major (5-10% of the project cost) prototype test facility necessary to establish feasibility and/or performance?
- If yes: Is the scope, schedule and cost for the test facility well established and part of the project cost?
- If no: do you rely on existing test facilities or similar operating machines? Which ones?

System status: The status of the various muon collider subsystems is summarized in several documents, for example in the IMCC ESPPU back-up document, chapter 1.4 [3].

Very briefly:

- Proton driver & target: Design established; spent-beam extraction remains an issue.
- Muon cooling studies: Strong emittance reduction achieved, transmission and absorber loads remain important topics of studies.
- Acceleration: Concepts in place and studied; performance sensitivity to lattice errors being studied.
- Collider ring: Energy acceptance and chromatic control studied, improvements underway; misalignments studies important.
- CERN option studied: Surface installations on CERN land; SPS and LHC tunnels reused; proton complex at Meyrin; cooling/linacs at Prévessin; injection into new 10 km ring.
- Fermilab option: Layout within site boundaries; study refining use of existing infrastructure and collider parameters.

TRLs: The TRL of the key components and software that constitutes the muon collider are summarized in Table 8. The future development of these components and tools, complemented by a demonstrator programme and detector and physics studies, form the basis for the IMCC R&D programme presented in the February 2025 LDG review (where this table was presented). The review committee report is available (see close out in [7]) and high-lighted in addition RF studies and progress as being under-represented in this overview. This was addressed in the subsequent planning and reports (see more in section 3.2), as the IMCC ESPPU documents [2, 3] and the recent IMCC International Advisory Committee review in June-July 2025 [8].

R&D programme: In order to address these challenges during the next decade an extensive R&D programme has been planned. The goal of the programme for the period 2026-2036 is to reach technical decision readiness by 2036-37 for a staged implementation of a muon collider. The programme requires about 320 MCHF material budget and around 2700 FTEy of personnel for the collider and detector R&D part over a ten-year time period. **See section 3.2 for more information.**

Risk mitigation plan: See previous section. While a careful risk identification and description of the subsequent required R&D form the basis of IMCC R&D planning, a formal risk mitigation plan for the construction phase is not available at this time.

Item	TRL 2026	TRL 2036	Comments
Target solenoid (HTS)	5	6-7	Model coil (20@20)
Final cooling solenoid (HTS)	3	6	UHF solenoid demonstrator (UHF-Demo)
Cooling cell RF	3	6-7 for the three	Cavities and klystrons
Cooling cell solenoid (HTS)	3		Split solenoid demonstrator (SOLID)
Integrated cell w/absorber	4		Cooling cell unit
Pulsed magnet (NC)	7	7	Fast pulsed magnet string
Integrated w/power converter	4	6-7	and associated power system (RCS-String)
SC magnets (HTS)	3	5-6*	Rectangular aperture dipole (MBHTS)
Collider ring NbTi	7	7	LHC type
Collider ring Nb3Sn	6	6-7	Wide-aperture Nb3Sn dipole (MBHY)
Collider ring HTS	3	5*	Wide aperture HTS dipole (MB-HTSY)
Acc. Design I	4	7-8**	S/E simulation, lattices
Acc. Design II	4	7**	Imperfections, Collective effects

Table 8: TRLs as presented in the Lab Director Group review in February 2025 [7].

*not needed for 3 TeV, **after five years

Required test-facility The Muon Cooling Demonstrator Programme is an essential component of the muon collider R&D programme. Muon cooling is required in order to deliver the required luminosities but it is a technology that has not been fully proven. The programme is described in more detail in section 3.3. A much more complete description of various steps, a schedule and options for implementation at CERN and/or FERMILAB can be found in chapter 12 of [3].

9 Performance

Provide:

- Expected uncertainty on nominal luminosity performance (instantaneous, integrated) and main sources of uncertainty
- Uncertainty on other performance parameters (power consumption, energy, availability, ...)
- Expected performance ramp-up timeline

9.1 Luminosity

Luminosity uncertainties arise from uncertainty on the beam size and flux at the interaction points. The beam flux estimate relies on accurate calculation of transmission through subsystems in the accelerator chain. Beam size uncertainty arises either from emittance uncertainty or uncertainty in the performance of the collider ring focusing system. The expected uncertainty arising from each subsystem is discussed below.

The proton driver is based on known technology although with some modifications. Existing facilities can achieve beam power beyond that required by the IMCC baseline. Nonetheless, the design requires short bunches. Validation of modelling in parameter space equivalent to the muon collider will reduce the risk. For example, experiments are planned at several facilities with perveance equivalent to the muon collider parameters.

The main uncertainty arising from the muon production and cooling system is in transmission. The final transverse emittance delivered is controlled by the equilibrium emittance in the final cooling system, which is physically well-understood. There is greater uncertainty in the longitudinal emittance growth in the final cooling, but this effects the luminosity only indirectly. Transmission through the system relies on good performance of intermediate stages and uncertainties are cumulative. Some parts of the muon production and cooling system are technologically demanding. Prototyping of RF cavities in magnetic fields, construction of a cooling module and finally demonstration of beam performance will control the transmission and emittance uncertainty of this system i.e. execution of the cooling Demonstrator programme. Several novel muon cooling concepts are under development that may lead to a significantly improved performance.

The acceleration system, following a full R&D programme, is expected to be relatively low risk. A modest emittance growth budget has been assigned to each stage to control uncertainty; losses will arise due to muon decays which are readily calculable. Even a drastic change in parameters will only result in relatively small change in performance.

The main uncertainty in the collider arises from uncertainty in the beam size at the interaction point, in particular in view of the need to move the beam periodically. Very tight focusing will be required which places strong demands on magnet systems. Further design work and magnet prototyping will mitigate this uncertainty. If mitigation of the neutrino flux is not possible, reduction in beam current in the collider ring may be a fall-back.

Beam-induced background, while not directly affecting luminosity, may degrade system performance and place practical limits on the luminosity that may be exploited. Mitigation of this risk requires detectors that are somewhat more demanding than HL-LHC; suitable R&D must be executed to deliver these instruments.

Overall uncertainty may be constrained through the implementation of an integrated design activity, which must be suitably resourced.

9.2 Power Consumption

The inventory of power requirements at this stage of development of the design was limited to power converters, RF systems and cryogenics, which are in any case the major contributors, together with the needs of the proton driver that were extracted from the ESS linac. The outcome of

the exercise is summarized in Table 9 for the two energy stages of the CERN scenario and for the Green Field installation. The table considers the power values estimated for the nominal operation.

Table 9: Power for the Muon Collider energy stages in the CERN scenario and Green Field installation. The higher collider power consumption for the 3.2 TeV at CERN is due to the use of low-temperature superconducting technology.

	Unit	CERN 3.2 TeV	CERN 7.6 TeV	Green Field 10 TeV
Proton Driver	MW	16.70	16.70	16.70
6D Cooling	MW	11.76	11.76	11.76
RLAs	MW	10.77	10.77	10.77
RCSs	MW	44.19	108.93	124.68
Collider	MW	10.00	4.10	4.10
General Cooling and Ventilation	MW	20.00	20.00	20.00
Total Power consumption	MW	113.42	172.26	188.01

At the moment, the power analysis includes the contributions from RF power sources, RCS normal conducting magnets, cryogenics for magnets and for RF, general cooling requirements associated to buildings and cryogenics. The cooling of normal conducting RF systems, like in the cooling channel, is not considered here.

9.3 Energy

IMCC is addressing the key risks for the energy and the proposed R&D programme will reduce the risk to the level that allows to commit to the project. Most important examples are:

- Magnet design studies established the field that can be achieved in the collider. The proposed model and prototypes will validate these fields. If the field goal were not achieved, increasing the collider ring size can still ensure the collision energy.
- Designs of the fast-ramping RCS dipoles and power converters predict the achievable field swing. Prototypes will validate them. If the fields were not achieved, increasing the size of the RCS during the design phase could maintain the energy. Implementation of the RCSs in existing tunnels could limit the final beam energy.
- In the RCS, reduced speed of the fast-ramping dipoles or reduced gradient of the RF cavities would be mitigated by increasing the number of turns, reducing the transmission and the luminosity in the percent range but preserving the collision energy.
- Designs studies of the RCSs and the collider ring identified their cost ranges. The proposed R&D will narrow their ranges, in particular through models and prototypes, to ensure that the cost of a proposed energy is sound.
- The studies established an estimate of the power consumption. The R&D programme will validate this estimate with models and prototypes.
- Studies of the neutrino flux indicate that a site at CERN appears possible. Further R&D will validate this.

9.4 Availability

The availability goal for the muon collider operation of 70% is similar to other circular colliders [2]. Table 10 shows the breakdown of the operation over the year. A detailed assessment of the required redundancies and overheads across the whole complex will be informed by the R&D programme that will provide failure rates of components.

According to the latest availability studies for the FCC-ee, the main factors limiting system performance are the power converters and the RF systems. Similarly, for the rapid cycling synchrotron (RCS), the main availability drivers are very likely the RF system and power converters.

Operational phase	Number of days	Fraction of the peak power consumption [%]	
		3.2 TeV	7.6 TeV
Annual shutdown	125	50	38
Commissioning	40	100	100
Technical stops	10 +5 (recovery)	62	61
Machine development	20	100	100
Downtime (faults)	49	72	71
Data taking	116	100	100

Table 10: Breakdown of the operational phase and the corresponding fractional power consumption.

Both accelerator complexes require a comparable number of cryomodules and use the same technology—superconducting radio frequency (SRF) cavities. The availability of the RF cavities is likely to limit the overall availability of the high-energy complex, thereby reducing the average luminosity. In the FCC-ee, power converters present a limitation due to the high number of magnet families. In the RCS, the challenge stems more from the need to handle tremendous peak power, despite the relatively low average power, as well as the stringent constraints on the ramp jitter to remain synchronized with the fast beam energy increase.

The availability of both the RF system and the power converters can be improved through redundancy, though this comes at a higher cost. The impact of failures on the operation can be mitigated by adding adequate overhead to gain operational margin.

Fig. 8: Neutrino exit points and directions from the long straight sections of the currently studied collider placement option in the local CERN area (left) and qualitative illustration of the neutrino exit point distance to the collider from all the interconnection elements of the collider arcs (right). Darker colour correspond to closer distances. The exit point sizes are not realistic, only illustrative.

10 Site Preparation Status

- Has a specific placement scenario been defined for the collider complex and its infrastructure and at which level (e.g. general geological considerations, detailed geological investigations, territorial compatibility, reservation of land, access to existing infrastructures, preparation or detailed plans, cost estimates. . .)?

A key challenge of a high-energy muon collider is the decay of muons in the collider ring, which can lead to a large local neutrino flux that can reach the Earth's surface even at significant distances from the collider. Rare single events of these high-energy neutrinos produce secondary particle showers to which members of the public may be exposed. The overall goal for the muon collider design is therefore to ensure that the impact of these showers is negligible. This is in line with CERN's environmental strategy, defined by the Horizon 2030 objectives, which set the goal of optimising the radiological impact of the Organization's activities and, specifically, keeping the radiological environmental impact due to ionising radiation on the reference population groups below a specific value.

A potential option for a Muon Collider placement in the local CERN area has been identified and is currently under study, taking into account neutrino-induced radiation and civil engineering constraints. It includes two access shafts within the CERN-owned domain, with the collider's orientation and inclination designed to mitigate the environmental impact from its neutrino flux emission.

The most critical areas of the collider in terms of neutrino flux emission are the long straight sections around the Interaction Points (IPs) housing the experiments. In the proposed placement option, mitigation of the neutrino flux from the IPs is achieved by directing it towards a distant area in the Mediterranean Sea on one side and towards a limited, non-built-up area in the mountains on the other. Figure 8 shows the directions of neutrinos originating from the IPs after exiting the Earth's surface as well as the exit point distances of neutrinos from the interconnection elements in the collider arcs. The pink lines represent aboveground neutrino trajectories, confirming that once they emerge from the ground, they do not re-enter. Further investigation on the height-depth clearance with the realistic IP neutrino distributions is part of the planned R&D program.

In the Mediterranean Sea, the neutrino flux exit points are located about 330 km from the collider. To obtain an effective dose estimate to members of the public for the case of the Mediterranean Sea, site-specific occupancy factors will need to be assessed, since no international guidelines exist for such cases; nevertheless these factors are expected to be very low.

In the mountain area, the neutrino flux would exit at around 20 km in a non-built-up area of limited size, which could be acquired by the Organization and fenced to restrict public access.

Inside this area, the highest initial effective dose rate estimate is of the order of the level in a plane, which corresponds to a low-occupancy Supervised Radiation Area according to CERN's area classification.

For the collider arcs, the maximum annual effective dose is currently estimated to be below the CERN goal from the bending region. This also includes the effect of the foreseen machine movers enabling vertical beam deformation within ± 1 mrad. Recent studies indicate that approximately 80 discrete deformation steps over the course of an operational year would be sufficient to achieve the dose reduction plateau when taking into account more realistic geometries and exposure scenarios. The estimate is moreover based on a conservative scenario in which the neutrino flux exits at 20 km distance from the collider into an inhabited area with 100% occupancy. Additional placement optimization may allow to avoid inhabited area at such short distances, which could reduce the assumed occupancy and the related dose estimate. Next to that, potential overlaps of the individual neutrino spots originating from different interconnection regions still need to be investigated. Possible further mitigation measures consist of horizontal closed orbit deformations and an increase of the vertical deformation amplitude of the movers.

It should be stressed that all the above-given dose estimates are preliminary. Final dose assessments will be based on representative persons from the public in combination with the detailed dose surface maps. To provide more reliable and fully optimized dose evaluations for members of the public, a comprehensive R&D program has been proposed. It shall also comprise the impact assessment from the high-energy acceleration stage.

It has been demonstrated that the neutrino-induced soil activation and transfer of activation products to groundwater are negligible. Conventional RP aspects connected to prompt and residual radiation, air, water and soil activation, as well as radioactive waste produced in the whole facility starting from the proton driver up to the collider ring are principally well understood and can be mitigated to acceptable levels as long as they are addressed in the design phase. An initial assessment of conventional RP aspects in the collider arcs indicated that, after five years of beam operation, radiation levels would remain below those expected in the HL-LHC inner triplet region and are therefore considered acceptable, provided interventions are optimised.

Utilizing the capabilities of the Geoprofiler software, an algorithm was developed to further optimize and fine tune the exact collider location and orientation. The main purpose of this algorithm is to maximize the distance at which the neutrinos from the collider might impact inhabited areas, while keeping the IP shafts contained within the CERN domain.

It has been confirmed via desktop studies that all the underground tunnels for the Muon Collider could be located within the good molasse rock, in well understood ground due to its proximity to existing CERN infrastructure. Unlike for FCC, the more challenging limestone rock can be avoided. The injection complex is sited entirely within CERN owned land on and adjacent to the Prévessin campus as is presented in Figure 9 below. As well as this, the interaction region surface facilities could be fully positioned on existing CERN land on the Meyrin and Prévessin campuses, thus overall, the project has minimal territorial impact. Further studies are ongoing to optimise the final alignment for the collider ring due to its neutrino radiation.

Fig. 9: Muon Collider Site Layout

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Answers of the International Muon Collaboration to the Questionnaire of the ESG Working Group on Knowledge Transfer and Innovation

Questions on innovation and industrialisation potential of future collider projects

The following set of questions will be posed to the future collider projects with dedicated input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU). Please consider how the future collider project is structured in terms of its innovation and industrialisation potential.

General remarks:

- “Technologies” includes hardware, firmware and software.
- When answering the questions, focus on maximum three technologies.

General transfer questions

1. Is knowledge transfer and innovation structurally embodied in your project?

Innovation and technology transfer are instrumental to develop the first muon collider. They are naturally embedded in the R&D programme both for accelerator and detector technologies. In many fields, the requirements will push beyond the state of the art: RF, magnets, targets, new detector technologies, etc. The choice of technologies has been consciously made to maximise the impact of anticipated developments and align with market potential, e.g. the HTS magnets baseline for 10 TeV.

While the IMCC has been formed only recently, formal connections to industrial and societal partners have started. They currently exploit existing structures in the laboratories (e.g. CERN KT group), universities and funding agencies (INFRA-DEV project MuCol). Industry is regularly consulted as to interest in the technology and latest advances. A few specific examples are (i) HTS materials (worldwide procurement of tapes at three manufacturers in 2024), (ii) HTS magnets (discussions and visits to three worldwide manufacturers in 2024 and 2025) and (iii) semiconductors (declaration of interest in rapidly pulsed converters in 2025). An explicit integration of technology transfer into the IMCC structure is being prepared.

2. Which transfer mechanism have you implemented in your project?

For most of the components we are still in a pre-conceptual design phase. R&D budget as proposed in the ESPPU submission is necessary to ramp up the development of the technology. The CERN KT group is already involved in the project. and we will leverage the potential in collaboration with them. Specific examples of knowledge and technology transfer already acted are: (i) signed agreements with major institutional actors of the nuclear fusion community, to share conceptual and engineering design of magnets of relevance to the muon collider and magnetically confined fusion, (ii) signed collaborations with industrial partners to jointly design and prospect the construction of HTS magnets, in particular high field solenoids (20 T), operated at high temperature (20 K) and with large bore (order of 1 m). IP clauses have been established according to standard CERN and international practices.

3. How do you realise IP protection like identification of inventions and confidential knowhow?

New technology developments are discussed with CERN's Knowledge Transfer group (and similar other bodies at the collaborating institutes), to understand their potential use outside the

project and the best exploitation strategy, which will be done on a case by case basis and might include open source licensing, patenting or other forms of IP protection. In general, background is identified prior to the work, and foreground is shared IP.

Innovation Potential

4. What are the unique conceptual and implemented technologies this project has already brought or will bring compared to existing solutions?

The three most important technologies with applications in society that are unique for the muon collider are:

- REBCO-based HTS magnets,
- Fast-switching, high-current power converters
- AI for real-time decision-making.

Many other technologies are also important for the muon collider but are omitted here. Some have less impact on society, e.g. the muon cooling technology or cavity couplers for high power. Some are shared with other accelerator projects, e.g. high-efficiency klystrons and damping couplers for the cavities as well as more efficient cryogenics. An additional important benefit of the studies is the training of early career researchers.

High Temperature Superconductor magnets, in particular REBCO operated at 20 K, are instrumental to the muon collider design. In contrast to other colliders, the magnets required cover a wide spectrum of configurations, fields and dimensions. In particular a wide range of solenoids is required, from highest fields at small apertures (40 T or more) to large aperture high-field solenoids (20 T) for the target. Magnet R&D for the muon collider (20 T large bore target solenoid) already has demonstrated impact on the nuclear fusion community. In particular the Study is already formally collaborating with several actors in fusion such as F4E, Eurofusion, ENI, Gauss Fusion Gesellschaft, and others. Also other fields of scientific and societal applications will profit from HTS magnet R&D for the muon collider, such as: (i) MRI, now moving to all-HTS helium-free systems for high performance and low maintenance, (ii) NMR, presently at the level of 30 T and moving steadily to higher fields, (iii) material and life sciences in high magnetic fields, where several institutes worldwide are developing all-superconducting 40 T user facilities, and (iv) generators for wind turbines and motors, requiring 3D compact and high field polar windings akin to accelerator magnets to increase power and torque density. If the project is attributed sufficient R&D funds, it will become the world leading project in the development of REBCO based magnets given the variety of magnets required and the size of the community formed (that involves today most of the European institutes active on SC magnets, and also some overseas collaborators, in particular the US Magnet Development Programme). In addition to advancing magnet technology, such R&D will spur the development of novel quench detection and protection strategies, high temperature cooling (helium, as well as alternative refrigerants such as hydrogen), radiation hardness, and in general all techniques and systems associated with magnet design, manufacturing and testing.

Fast-switching, high-current power converter are being developed for the pulsed synchrotrons of the muon collider, based on IGBTs or IGCTs. The novel concept is modular and enables flexible, dynamic pulse shape control via selective activation of power cells; this shifts the pulse

shaping from the hardware to the control layer, which uses Iterative Learning Control. Infineon already manifested interest in collaborating in a joint development programme. This has potential applications to fusion reactors, the power grid and satellite payload launchers.

AI for real-time decision-making, being explored in the context of detector reconstruction and data acquisition. In muon colliders, the main source of detector hits comes from the presence of beam-induced backgrounds, which are uncorrelated with the physics signal. The background can be significantly reduced by detector design and the ability to discriminate with high precision between signal and background energy depositions, drastically reducing the required offline processing resources and/or the detector readout power consumption.

New heterogeneous computing architectures are being investigated (potentially including quantum technologies) for online off-detector event selection and reconstruction, as well as neuromorphic chip architectures (which could even be deployed on-detector). Current efforts are focused on track reconstruction, one of the most computationally demanding tasks in high-energy physics.

AI algorithms can then effectively exploit correlations among particle features to perform precise event-by-event discrimination in real time. Their ability to handle high-dimensional data and identify patterns makes them particularly powerful in selecting different signal events. This capability opens the door to innovative trigger strategies and dynamic data reduction schemes at the hardware level.

These AI approaches differ from language-based models and could have wide applications in the automation of time-sensitive or stressful tasks, such as real-time industrial safety systems or autonomous vehicles. In addition, some of the methods developed for HEP (i.e. track reconstruction) can be adapted to broader classes of optimization problems, such as logistics and network optimization.

The relatively clean topology of muon collision events offer an ideal place to apply the current emerging quantum algorithms. Quantum computing approaches could complement classical AI by tackling specific tasks where quantum advantage is expected, such as complex correlation analysis.

The Study will also address **other technologies** such as development of high-efficiency klystrons, new materials for target technology, beam windows, high-power RF couplers, fast cavity tuners, efficient high-order mode dampers, low-level RF, investigation and mitigation of RF breakdown, more efficient cryogenics, exploration of use of liquid hydrogen for cooling and others. Detector technologies such as radiation-hard, low-power “smart pixels” or longitudinally segmented semi-homogeneous crystal calorimeters (CRILIN) are key parts of the Study. Many of these technologies are shared with other projects and can likely be employed in medical applications and homeland security. Others are in exploration state, e.g. the use of liquid hydrogen for cryogenics, but might potentially have synergy with the use of hydrogen as energy storage in a green grid.

5. What unmet needs or problems do these new technologies address, and how are the new or foreseen solutions superior to current practices?

This is partly covered in the reply to the previous question. The challenges are high magnetic fields (up to 40 T, and higher), high RF gradients in magnetic field, high power on target (2÷4

MW), development of comprehensive simulation tools, including beam dynamics, beam matter interactions, electromagnetic fields, collective effects etc. moreover, advanced reconstruction techniques and algorithms will be necessary in the detectors, advancing our understanding and diffusion of Machine learning and Artificial intelligence.

The high-field, large-aperture target magnet allows efficient capture of the produced muons. The power converters have to operate in a regime that is not used in accelerators. They have to provide a short, well controlled, high-power current pulse to achieve an almost linear ramp of the magnets.

6. Have the technologies resulted in any intellectual properties rights (IPR) like patent filings, proprietary methods, confidential knowhow or novel applications of existing technologies?

As the study is recent, production of IPR is only starting, but promising. For example, we do have some confidential know-how already in HTS magnets: (i) means to build large bore solenoids with high-current soldered cables, (ii) simultaneous winding and soldering of HTS solenoids, (iii) new winding configurations for HTS dipoles. Funding of the hardware development will be instrumental to realise the potential.

7. How do you integrate utilization strategies for specific technologies and components in the collider project?

For the already identified synergistic technologies, we aim to collaborate directly with the relevant scientific collaborations and industry as well as to obtain support from the collaboration and co-funding from organisations such as the European Union. An example of utilization in other HEP projects is the work within the scope of the High Field Magnet (HFM) R&D Programme, where solenoids R&D is assigned a specific work package. Technologies and industrial procurement specific to the Muon Collider solenoids will then profit other HEP projects that are in the scope of HFM, such as the FCC-hh. An example of utilization in industry is the collaboration with ENI, where CERN will provide technical coordination of the construction of a model coil demonstrating the target solenoid, while ENI will provide project control and a large part of funding. The benefits to both partners are increased readiness and risk reduction towards the applications of interest: muon collider for CERN and magnetically confined fusion for ENI. With sufficient R&D funding, we will expand this process systematically to other magnet types (see list of fields impacted reported earlier) and other systems.

Some of the technologies are disruptive and we may face a potential competition between different regions. We will develop a strategy to deal with this.

**8. How adaptable are these technologies across different types of construction projects or geographical contexts?
In what other fields of research or economy can they be applied?**

The magnet technologies developed by the Muon Collider study will benefit any future collider, including FCC-hh, provided sufficient funding is invested to develop the technologies before 2040. They can be applied in many other fields such as magnetically confined fusion, MRI, NMR, electric power generation and transport, medical applications. The detector technologies and software

concepts will benefit all future detectors, in particular a potential FCC-hh detector that will be exposed to very high background level. The development of radiation-hard micro-electronics will be beneficial for other fields that need radiation hardness, e.g. in space applications or in control systems in high radiation environment in general. The use of AI for real-time decision making (potentially in conjunction with quantum devices) will likely drive the field in all future HEP-applications and has a large transfer potential to automation tasks through industry. .

9. Which IP strategy do you have with respect to hardware, firmware and software?

We are still developing a complete strategy, which will depend on funding, the technology, on the market that will be addressed, and on the presence of interested entrepreneurs.

The detector simulation and reconstruction software is open-source and publicly available on github. Open-source licenses such as GPLv3, Apachev2 and MIT are used throughout the software stack.

10. How do you describe the technologies resulting from your project in terms of their contribution to the current societal challenges? Please highlight what specific contribution your innovations can make?

The development of HTS magnets for the muon production will facilitate solutions for magnetically confined fusion, which is one of the ingredients to satisfying energy needs and counteract climate change. HTS technology for compact and high field solenoids required for muon cooling can translate directly into applications for helium-free medical imaging (MRI), making the technology more readily available, and ultra-high-field NMR. Development of successful winding methods for dipoles and quadrupoles could be applied to the polar winding of HTS motors and power generators, such as required for offshore windmills.

The power converter technology required for the muon accelerators has potential applications in more effective management of transients in the electrical power distribution grid, needing fast adjustments, and fusion reactors, which require accurate shaping and repeatability of high-current pulses. It could therefore also contribute to improving energy production and distribution, thus mitigating climate change. The technology could also have application in payload launchers for satellites.

Real-time AI has a vast realm of application, from automation in industrial applications, self-driving vehicles and logistics. These applications could have wide-ranging effects, from the decrease production costs for industrial products, contributing to the democratisation of transport, and energy efficiency.

11. Do the technologies/applications you describe above carry risks, for example in case of accident or sabotage, or are they of a dual-use nature?

No risks are foreseen in case of accident or sabotage. If dual use is identified for components they will be tracked and accounted for according to the regulations in effect at the partner institutions, as in previous colliders and detectors.

Some technologies have the potential to be disruptive and may require careful considerations as they are relevant for regional competitiveness and sovereignty.

Industrialisation Potential

12. Have you involved industrial partners in the project or do you plan to involve them with an active role?

And for which technologies is cooperation with industrial partners specifically encouraged and what are the contribution of the industrial partners?

Collaborations with several institutional and industrial partners exists for HTS magnet development, in particular F4E and Eurofusion (institutional), and ENI, Gauss Fusion Gesellschaft (industrial). Contacts have been established with several other industrial partners (Tokamak Energy, CFS, ASG to cite a few). This was motivated by the interest of industry in taking part in the project from an early stage, as well as the potential for learning from industry development to the benefit of the Muon Collider development.

Infineon expressed interest in collaborating on a joint development programme for the power converter technology.

The quantum devices by IBM have been used to benchmark the use of quantum algorithms. A survey of industrial partners for the deployment of quantum devices on-premise will be performed, if demonstrated to be the optimal solution, at a later stage. Intel's neuromorphic chips are being investigated, but no direct connections to the industrial partner have been made yet. Detector micro-electronics (and sensors) are developed with industry when the dedicated technologies and the amount of components will require it.

However, more funding for the study is required to exploit and expand these collaborations. This is critical to maintain industry engaged.

13. What elements of the project or of the discussed technologies are modular, standardisable, or suitable for prefabrication, automation or mass production in industry?

In principle all, acknowledging that for components of high technological content the units produced will never be counted in millions.

14. What are the main barriers to scaling these technologies for widespread use (e.g., cost, training, logistics, regulation, legal frameworks, legal binding standards and norms)?

The main contribution of the muon collider study is to develop the technology to a level that it can be scaled by industry to large-scale use, this includes mostly TRL levels up to 7. The demonstration of the technologies is the first important step. HEP laboratories have a successful track record in this, bringing concepts (TRL 3...4) to the level required for industrial interest and production (TRL 6...7). At this moment the lack of a sufficient funding level is the obstacle that hinders the development.

The technologies developed pose no anticipated issue for their use. Application in the fusion reactors, if successful, will certainly require an attentive analysis of the regulatory frameworks

related to reliability, availability and safety that go beyond the level required for a collider. This is an on-going matter of discussion among institutional and industrial partners in the field, and will not hinder development for HEP.

15. Have the solutions demonstrated performance at scale or undergone testing in a real-world or simulated environment?

The funding of the proposed R&D programme will enable us to demonstrate the proposed technologies.

16. What partnerships, supply chain inputs, or systems are required to industrialise the technologies?

The proposed technologies are not yet state-of-the-art. It will therefore be necessary to build up a supply chain in collaboration with industry that is able to provide the necessary quality. This is similar to what was done for LEP or LHC. It is nonetheless crucial to build strong links with industrial suppliers of critical technologies already at this stage of the R&D, so that the industrial partners can understand and adjust to future HEP needs. One example where this is most striking is HTS conductor, which is today tailored and dominated by fusion applications. The R&D program for the Muon Collider foresees targeted conductor orders to raise awareness and initiate the required adjustments on the side of the perspective conductor manufacturers. Response so far is very good.

17. To what extent are the solutions repeatable across different projects, and how much site-specific adaptation is needed?

We do not anticipate any site dependence for the application of the developed technologies; with the obvious exception of placement studies. The requirements of other colliders as presently proposed are in most cases less challenging, either in the level of field or for the aperture of the magnets, therefore any development will largely cover the other proposals. Target technologies are common to those of high intensity neutron sources or Radioactive ion beam facilities, and collaborations in the field are already active. The development of high efficiency klystrons is common already to other projects and might require the establishment of a European lab able to build prototypes in collaboration or in total autonomy from industry. Mitigation of RF breakdown is common to any high intensity accelerator.

Collaborative efforts are already on-going on detector technologies and software concepts developments, expected to be directly essential for high energy hadron-hadron colliders. The more favorable Muon Collider radiation environment can make an adaptation of industrial solutions more straightforward.